

Social Media Marketing of Micro Business Entities

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Abstract:- This study investigated the lived experiences of micro business owners and managers in relation to the perceived effectiveness of using social media marketing. The paper utilized the phenomenological research design covering ten micro business owners as participants to answer the main problem about the effects of social media platforms to the sales and marketing. The participants were primarily asked to answer the interview questions. Respondents came from two micro business industry sector viz. retail/ wholesale and foods service industry. In the study, the result generated three major themes from the interview: the strong business and marketing viability, interactive and promising platform channel; and online customers behavior and feedback whereas ten key subthemes emerged from each major themes.

Keywords:- Social Media Marketing, Micro Business Entities, Strong Marketing Viability, Interactive and Promising Platform, Online Customer Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

The internet and web technologies facilitate efficient and effective marketing activities and many business organizations are using online marketing trends to promote and advertise their products and services. In modern business, social media marketing is largely considered as a promising platform to conduct the promotional activities as to effectively communicate with the targeted customers (Popp & Woratschek, 2016).

According to Rouse (2019) the goal of social media marketing is to produce content that users will share with their social network to help a company increase product exposure and broaden customer reach. This type of marketing is done through various social media marketing platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and more to promote website circulation to engage user's interactivity. Successful social media marketing is done when companies create content that entice customers and others audience to share it on their social media outlets.

Micro business entities nowadays, use social media marketing and they have become part of many people's lives. Many people update their social media, every minute, every hour, every day as forms of electronic communication through which users create online communities to share information, ideas, personal messages, and other content. It also provides a platform for business consumers to advertise their personal evaluations and preference for a products and services that they want to avail. Social media, including

networks, microblogging, vlogs, live streaming and forums, transform internet users from passive receivers to active learners, by facilitating interactivity and engagement in business communication (Grabowicz, 2014).

Micro business entities have an imperative role to play in the economic development of the country (Sharmilee, 2016) and most business publicity using the social media marketing appeals to influence the way how business consumers view themselves and how buying a certain product can prove to be beneficial and effective. Micro business entities are now having the ability to engage in business through the use of different social media marketing platforms to influence consumer behavior in unheralded ways by engaging the business customers to develop brand-centric communities in such a way that ties customers to their products and services. Nowadays, almost all businesses are done over the internet, from payment of bills, buying foods and clothing, hotels, restaurant and tourist bookings, magazine and newspaper subscription and most specially shopping. The number of online sales sites is increasing, and their use has greatly helped the consumers in making purchase transactions as the society today are having the convenience for on-line spending (Anand et al., 2019).

Currently, Facebook is considered as the primary medium to socialize. Micro business entities used digital-based technology to quickly disseminate knowledge and information to a huge number of users. They allow creation and exchange of user-generated content via Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube. The size and the geographic location of a business nowadays do not matter in on-line business because globalization has triggered the advancement of technology, which enforce many companies to use digital business and current trend in social media marketing to fulfill the needs of internationalization and competitive advantage in emerging markets (Wagner & Mainardes et al., 2019).

Facebook as a social networking is very relevant and in-demand with most people spending more than hour online; and the business today is being transformed from a transactional relationship to a social relationship. It is now more critical than ever that successful businesses use engagement of social media marketing principles to plan for a successful and effective basis for customer allegiance and engagement. According to Godin (2014), the advertising and promotion of a product and services in social media diverges from the traditional product and service marketing because social media advertising is an inordinate entity that works along and continuum that is ever-evolving.

Dissanayake & Nandasena (2020) mentioned that social media marketing adaptations increase the efficacy of the business for every company. Anyone who has access to the internet can transact from one business to another easily. Business is tasked to reinvent their intensive strategies to keep their customers with the current trends in social media marketing throughout time. Increase in the business finances and continuous communication are some benefits of social media marketing (Leen, 2020).

The Lovely Professional University, (2012) mentioned that on-line marketing business is the best tool for knowledge sharing that move forward into operational effectiveness, profits and competitive advantage. It is also refers to the utilization of cybernetics in business activities and uses technology as the buying and selling of goods and services over electronics mechanism such as the internet and other computer aided technology (Harsono, 2015).

Arceo, Cumahig, De Mesa et.al (2018) stated that social media continue to break geographical boundaries and connect people together and has revolutionized the way people interact and socialize with each other in various forms like social networking sites, vlogs, wikis, and microblogging sites. The most widely adopted social media platforms are to Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and content sharing website (Pham & Gammoh, 2015). Businesses and entrepreneurs alike have taken advantage of these online trends as marketing platforms to grow and expand their businesses that are very prevalent in firm strategies and yet, little is known about the factors that drive success for promotion of online product brand and services (Hudges et al,2018).

Several preliminary works have documented the importance of social media in improving micro business sustainability (Kang & Park, 2018; Taneja & Toombs, 2014). Social media is not only effective in helping micro business growth (Dahnil et al., 2014), but also as a consumer media to easily access new products and services (Dženopoljac et al., 2016). Social media is also a means for people to be engaged in online activities, market and even become an effective comparison in decision making (Chatterjee & Kumar Kar, 2020). In addition, social media has become a kind of bridge between micro business entities and the potential consumer community (Abed et al., 2015). Generally, Tripopsakul (2018) noted that effective use of social media can enhance productivity and business revenue.

Despite the proliferation of social media and the widespread adoption of those diverse marketing trends as effective communication tools and platforms, many small and medium business enterprises still opt to substantiate the studies that will investigate the perceived effectiveness of the current trends in social media marketing since many micro business entities encounter similar concerns towards promoting their products and services using a different social media marketing platform. This study aims to examine the effectiveness of using the social media marketing in selected micro business entities in Baliwag, Bulacan. Specifically, through qualitative research, this

study is designed to analyze and investigate the lived experiences of micro business entities owners and managers relative to the effectiveness of using social media marketing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MME's) in the Philippines*

According to the Senate of the Philippines (2012), MSME's are a vital factor in economic development in countries like the Philippines. These SMEs improved the lives of many Filipinos by creating jobs and stimulating economic growth in rural and far-flung areas. In 2014, according to a report provided by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), 99.6 % of the establishments in the Philippines was MSMEs and with the remaining 0.4 % are large companies (DTI, 2014).

MSMEs have contributed 62.8 per cent of jobs in 2014 compared to 37.1 % from large enterprises. It also contributes to exports accounting for 25 % revenue and estimated that 60 % of all exporters belong to this sector. SMEs presented a thriving and growing economy and served as a framework and a model for new entrepreneurs and large firms. Even with the policies supporting and promoting an empowering atmosphere for SMEs development, full growth and potential are hardly achieved, because of some non-financial and financial barriers (Senate of the Philippines, 2012).

Survival and continuity of this sector are necessary and essential for the country; hence, adopting technology innovations such as cloud computing can help reduce barriers as they can explore new business opportunities, maximize their profit and investments by integrating new strategies and cutting cost on Information Technology (IT) infrastructures. Adopting Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) enables business organizations to compete on a global scale with improved operation, productivity and services to customer and communication with its suppliers (Tarutė & Gatautis, 2014).

The Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), (2016) reported the improvement of the Philippines Cloud Readiness ranking it being the ninth most cloud-ready nation in the Asia Pacific, overtaking Thailand. Accordingly, the Philippines has improved on addressing freedom of information and privacy. Inadequate connectivity and exposure to natural disasters pose risks, reported as the reasons why the country performs poorly in these metrics. On the other hand, the Philippines has established Government Cloud (GovCloud), a government core objective of creating infrastructure and services that consolidate IT resources, streamline the organization cost in IT implementation and improve overall operational efficiency (Government Cloud, 2017). Accordingly, most Philippine agencies are having real potential and capabilities to implement cloud-based solutions and are benefitting from these technologies.

➤ *Categories of Micro and Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (MSMEs)*

Business exists in different forms and sizes. A business can be undertaken on a small scale, medium scale or large-scale basis. Since growth has been identified as a major business objective, it is rational to believe that a small business can grow to become large, and when it is still growing it can be referred to as a medium scale business. A business is considered small is relative depending on individual perception. The term small- scale enterprises or small business varies in meaning from one country to another and from one industry to another.

MSMEs are important part of a nation's economic and social structure as they play very important roles in creating employment opportunities for the growing labor force. The role of business enterprises is essential in pulling up the country's economic development. MSMEs exert a strong influence on the economies of all countries, particularly in developing countries.

In the Philippines, MSMEs play vital roles not only in wealth creation but also in dispersing new industries to the countryside that contributes to a more equitable distribution of income, encouraging entrepreneurial development, stimulating gainful employment, and supporting export growth. To encourage the development of MSMEs, the Government of the Philippines enacted into law the Magna Carta of Small Enterprises (Republic Act 6977) which outlines the general policies for the development of SMEs. Given their economic and social importance, Philippine SMEs are considered to be vital in the recovery of the national economy.

The Philippine MSME sector is composed of micro, small and medium enterprises engaged in industry, trading, agribusiness and services. MSMEs are defined as any business activity or enterprise engaged in industry, commerce, agribusiness and/or services, whether single proprietorship, partnership, cooperative or corporation, whose total assets, inclusive of those arising from loans but exclusive of the land on which the particular business entity's office, plant and equipment are situated must have value falling under the following categories: microenterprises have less than Php1.5 million in total assets and 1-9 employees; small-enterprises have Php1.5 million to Php15 million up to Php100 million in total assets and 10-99 employees; and, medium-enterprises have more than Php15 million up to Php100 million in total assets and 100-199 employees (Magna Carta of Small Enterprises RA 6977, as amended by RA 8289). As of 2006, there are 783,065 business enterprises operating in the Philippines; 99.7% or 780,469 are MSMEs and the remaining 0.3% or 2,596 are large enterprises. Of the total number of MSMEs, 92% or 720,191 are micro enterprises, 7.3% or 57,439 are small enterprises, and only 0.4% or 2,839 are medium enterprises.

Majority of the MSMEs in operation in 2006 can be found in the National Capital Region (NCR), with 194,549 business establishments; Region 4-A (CALABARZON) with 113,581; Region 3 (Central Luzon) with 84,175;

Region 6 (Western Visayas) with 46,195; and Region 1 (Ilocos Province) with 44,085. These top five locations accounted for about 61.8% of the total number of MSME establishments in the country.

➤ *MSME's Sectoral and Geographical Distribution*

The top five (5) industry sectors according to the number of MSMEs in 2020 were: (1) Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles (445,386); (2) Accommodation and Food Service Activities (134,046); (3) Manufacturing (110,916); (4) Other Service Activities (62,376); and (5) Financial and Insurance Activities (45,558). These industries accounted for about 83.77% of the total number of MSME establishments, (Department of Trade and Industry, 2006).

Majority of the MSMEs can be found in the National Capital Region (NCR) with 201,123 (21.10%) business establishments, Region 4-A (CALABARZON) with 139,363 (14.62%), Region 3 (Central Luzon) with 111,262 (11.68%), Region 7 (Central Visayas) with 65,682 (6.89%), and Region 6 (Western Visayas) with 57,469 (6.03%). These top five (5) locations accounted for about 60.33% of the total number of MSME establishments in the country. Regional concentration of MSMEs is largely associated with economic activity and population size. MSMEs generated a total of 5,380,815 jobs or 62.66% of the country's total employment. The micro enterprises produced the biggest share (29.38%) closely followed by small enterprises (25.78%) while medium enterprises were far behind at 7.50%. Meanwhile, large enterprises generated a total of 3,206,011 jobs or 37.34% of the country's overall employment.

In terms of value added, the MSME sector contributed 35.7% of the total with manufacturing contributing the largest share of 6.87%. Wholesale and retail trade and repair contributed 6.58% followed by financial intermediation with a share of 6%.

Within the sector, small enterprises accounted for the largest share of 20.5%. Medium enterprises followed with a share of 10.3% while micro enterprises registered a share of 4.9%. Among small enterprises, wholesale and retail trade and repair contributed the most with a share of 4.07% followed by manufacturing with a share of 3.82% while financial intermediation was next with a share of 3.35%.

For medium enterprises, manufacturing accounted for the biggest share of 2.77% followed by electricity, gas and water with a share of 1.92% and financial intermediation with 1.87%. For micro enterprises, wholesale and retail trade and repair represented the largest contribution of 1.73%.

➤ *Social Media Marketing*

Social media marketing (SMM) can be defined as a form of internet marketing that utilizes social networking websites as a marketing tool (Rouse, 2019). Social media marketing is largely considered by modern business as promising platforms to conduct the promotional activities as

to effectively communicate with the targeted customers (Popp & Woratschek, 2016; Harrigan et al., 2016; Gao & Feng, 2016; Kohli et al., 2016).

Facebook was able to generate more than 5.4\$ billion from advertising with growing percent up to 58%. Furthermore, Facebook revenue from advertising has grown by 59 % during the past year to over \$5.4 billion in 2014 (Facebook, 2014), which is testament to the shift from traditional media advertising to digital interactive media advertising by organizations. Such growing interest could be returned to the high level of attractiveness and interactivity existing in social media platforms (Swani et al., 2016; Wu, 2016).

In recent years, the use of social media has increased significantly (Thota, 2018). The growth of social media platforms has transformed the dynamics of the electronic marketplace by creating social networks of consumers, opinion leaders, and field experts (Samet, 2020). Kumar et al. (2020) illustrated the importance of social media marketing when they found that integrated marketing promotional messages can be effective at influencing consumers' perceptions about product image and lead to consumption behaviors. Indeed, promotional campaign conducted via social media could lead to reach different marketing goals with regards to customer experience, perception, awareness, knowledge, preferences, intention to buy, and actual purchasing (Duffett 2015).

In the light of the importance of social media in the advertising area, a fair number of studies have addressed the associated issues of promotional activities conducted in the social media platforms (Chang et al., 2015). Almost 89% have supported the role of social media in enhancing the impact of promotional activities on the customer's perception and awareness. Duffett (2015) discussed that the efficiency and effectiveness of social media advertising activities largely depend on how customers could perceive and formulate their attitudes toward such activities.

Thota (2018) argues that businesses can use social media to activate consumers' product needs by triggering brand conversations that promote positive perceptions about products, services, or ideas. Citing Starbucks as an example while the brand has a global presence, it continues to engage the marketplace with social media to generate felt needs (i.e. problem recognition) by sustaining consumers' brand awareness. In addition, Starbucks consistently deploys virtual messaging to promote consumers' preference for their brand in the marketplace. Social media is a powerful tool for message exposure. Thota (2018) found that 93% of U.S. businesses use Facebook and other platforms, such as Twitter and LinkedIn. As such, social media provides businesses with virtual avenues to enhance consumers' product/brand awareness.

Social media platforms are also used for consumer-to-consumer interactions to share their product/brand experiences (Thota, 2018). As such, social media offers businesses a means to generate brand awareness for their

products or services. For example, using owned media, businesses can post brand content related to their products and services. Awareness and excitement for brands can also be generated with paid media, such as boosted Facebook posts, in order to activate recognition of a need/problem that the brand can resolve. In addition, posts by consumer peers and opinion leaders can provide brand influencing stimuli. For example, Jashari and Rustemi (2017) assert that consumers' exposures to different social media posts, like photos, videos, reviews, etc. about the products trigger or prompt recognition of needs.

Micro business entities may also encourage customers to post-product purchases with the hopes of activating the product need stage within consumers. Utilization of macro-influencers to help build product awareness is also a common practice among businesses attempting to build brands on social media. Businesses can hire elite influencers (e.g., celebrities and athletes) to post-favorable information about their products (Wertz, 2019). This practice is effective because many highly paid macro-influencers (i.e., opinion leaders) have millions of followers on their social media platforms. All such content posted by these opinion leaders has the potential to influence the consumer decision-making process.

➤ *Facebook as Social Network Marketing*

SNM or social network marketing provides a way for business to reach and target current and potential customers with creative ads and messages. Digital marketers create campaigns that have specific goals and create ads within those campaigns to help them reach their business goals. Facebook is the most popular for social networking site in the world (Freeman et al. 2014). As of March 2015, 1.44 billion users accessed the site at least monthly and 936 million accessed the site daily (Facebook, 2015). Facebook app development has also stimulated mobile access with 798 million daily mobile users (Facebook, 2015). Social network marketing, commonly in Facebook, is any form of marketing that takes place on social media platforms. This marketing strategy can play out in many different ways, from formal advertising campaigns to informal customer engagement.

Since November 2007, Facebook embraced companies and commercial brands developing their own Facebook pages; and thus establish their own marketing online identities (Freeman et al. 2014). Companies can post images, videos, links, offers, competitions and a range of other digital media to their page timelines (Freeman et al. 2014). Consequently, potentially harmful commodity industries are able to frame their image, engage and interact with consumers, and evade legislative barriers (Brodmerkel & Hernandez, 2014). When consumers 'like' a company page to receive timeline updates, any consumer engagement with company pages may appear in the news feed of another Facebook user (Freeman et al. 2014).

Facebook clearly states in their Legal Terms that users are not allowed to provide fake information and that they must keep their information up to date (Legal Terms 2012).

This clearly indicates that the accuracy and correctness of Facebook user data is important for Facebook's business model. Inaccurate or false information endangers the sustainability of the Facebook business model. On the other hand, the Facebook platform attracts companies to use the platform for advertising and marketing by offering them a high number of users who are easy to access.

Using methods for detecting and eliminating fake profiles would lead to a reduction in registered accounts, raising the risk of eliminating false positives and making it more difficult for regular users to create and maintain a profile. It was also considered helpful for a successful Initial Public Offering (IPO) in May 2012 to have as many accounts as possible. Organizations, the service platform, and the individual users have different interests concerning data access and sharing. Whereas the platform and third parties, such as for-profit organizations that use the platform for business, are interested in gathering as much user data as possible, the users mostly do not want to share their personal data with them. However, as the data-sharing model of Web 2.0 services differs from traditional web applications, are often unaware who they are sharing their information with. Facebook provides data access control and privacy regulations to protect its users' privacy. However, in many cases the user is not sufficiently protected and private information is leaked.

➤ *Instagram as Micro-blog Marketing*

Instagram is the fourth most popular social media platform in the world (used by 60.6% of Internet users aged 16–64). It ranks right after YouTube (92.8%), Facebook (89.2%) and Facebook Messenger (76.5%) (Kemp, 2021). In Poland, it is used by nearly 9.2 million people (Kemp 2021), mainly young people aged 15–34 (Miotk, 2018). The history of the service dates back to 2010, when it emerged as an app for sharing photos. Initially, only iOS users were given this opportunity, but in 2012 Android users joined them. The app's name comes from a combination of the words "instant camera" and "telegram". The original idea of Instagram was to create a social medium to serve as a photo album. Later, new features emerged, such as the option to add video (2013), Instagram stories in 2016 and Instagram Television (IGTV) in 2018. To this day, the application gives the opportunity to interact by means of comments under posts, private messages, liking the posted material and creating a community gathered around a given profile (Czarnota, 2017, p. 136).

Instagram is a product designed mainly for mobile devices. There is a browser-based version, but it lacks several features available on mobile phones. The platform mainly operates with images and video, which means that it is treated as a medium focused on visual communication, aesthetics and entertainment. This makes it difficult to adapt the information content to its specifics (Buczek, 2016, p. 48). The visual message on Instagram can be intensified by "hashtags" words or phrases preceded by the sign. They allow posts to be assigned to relevant topic groups and make it easier to search for profiles on the platform. Instagram has also provided a hashtag tracking option, making it easier for

profile managers to quickly analyse who is using their company name, slogan etc. (Fabijańczyk, 2016). The use of hashtags strengthens the organic reach of posted content. Hashtags increase the marketing activity of company accounts and support sales actions. Proper use of this feature helps redirect potentially interested visitors directly to the shopping site, and can also be used to maintain relationships with other Instagram users. Emoticons are textual or pictorial records of emotions and moods. Although they are most often perceived as forms created in the era of computerization, they were used as early as 19th century (Tomić et al. 2013, p. 35). Nowadays, they are not only representations of standard American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII) characters, but also a graphic representation (image) of feelings or actions; Filters are type of overlay that add special effects to the content being shared. Instagram has many filters built into the application, and it is also possible to create individual ones. This feature is criticized because it leads to the creation of an idealized image of the presented world, life, or people.

Every now and then, a debate arises over the removal of some filters from Instagram (Youn, 2019) in order to compensate for the problem of dysmorphia or to change the way "filtered" messages are tagged. Wielgosz (2017) mentions the following advantages of Instagram communication: the mobile nature of the application and its functions, its user-friendly interface, its characteristic functionalities and the categorization of content. The aforementioned functions make profiles more attractive, multimediate them, strengthen their networking by establishing close relations with other users, and help build a coherent, interactive and visually attractive message.

On the other hand, features that reduce Instagram's marketing effectiveness are pointed out. Serafinelli (2017) remarks that Instagram since it includes limited features, it tends to be not as effective as other in terms of communication. It should be noted that Instagram, as a social medium operating with a visual message, is different from services such as Facebook or Twitter: hence, the marketing potential of the strategy depends on (Chobot 2019, pp. 51–55). In other words, the key to achieving effectiveness is an appropriate strategy for operating in this space (Buczek 2017; Hu et al. 2014), often involving the integration of marketing impact by linking to Facebook and Twitter (Hubinová, 2017). It is also worth noting the relatively high marketing potential of Instagram among the so-called generation Y. It comes second, after Facebook, and before Twitter and YouTube (Kusá and Záziková 2017).

Instagram's primary advantage over other social media platforms is its visual nature. If one has a business that benefits from the design of your product or if the service offers a visibly noticeable end result, Instagram is the best platform to showcase that content. Video, imagery, and illustration are all great contents that fits for this social media platform, but the marketing strategy will ultimately determine what type of content to publish and how often to post it. Establishing a strategy before diving right into a new social media platform, no matter how well it works for

everyone else's business, will be focused on the goals and most importantly the audience.

Instagram is one of many social media applications that the internet population is using on a daily basis. It is a simple photo-taking and photo-sharing application that was released on October 6, 2010 created by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger. According to Instagram (2015), as cited in (Dennis, 2014), Instagram first started off with providing functions on editing and sharing photos and later on added in the functions of sharing videos and photo messaging directly to another user. Instagram allows users to snap photo or video anywhere they are at any time and share it with their followers nationally and also internationally (Jadhav & Kamble & Patil, n.d.).

When looking under the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on Instagram's website, the application is defined as a fun and quirky way to share your life with friends through a series of photos (Instagram, 2015). The application allows one to use their mobile phone to snap a photograph, choose a filter to transform the image, and post it on the application. Everyone who creates an account on Instagram has a profile and news feed. Every user profile has a set of "Followers" and "Following" counts which represent how many people they follow and how many users are following them (Webtrends, 2015).

To interact with other people, you can double tap an Instagram post to "like it" or you can comment on the post by tapping on the comment button. To find other accounts to follow, you can press the Search tab. You can also find people by looking through suggested photos or a list of people. As the application continued to develop, more features were added. On January 2011, Instagram added the use of hashtags to help users discover both photographs and each other.

Facebook acquired Instagram in April 2012 for \$1 billion. Instagram continued to grow by 23% while Facebook only grew by 3% (Digital Trends, 2013). In December 2014, Instagram co-founder Kevin Systrom announced that Instagram has 300 million users accessing the site per month. When looking at the demographics of Instagram users, over 90% of the users are under the age of 35. Business Insider states that Instagram is largely made up of urban, youthful demographics with a significant skew toward women. Specifically, 68% of the users are female and 32% are male. With the heavy use of Instagram, companies have found this to be new niche for marketing.

➤ *Twitter as an Interactive Communications Marketing Medium*

Twitter and micro blogging are forms of blogging that limit the size of each post. The personal usage of Twitter by individuals provides a unique data source on individuals who are usually difficult to reach, such as entrepreneurs. For example, recent studies using Twitter data explore the personalities and psychological characteristics of superstar entrepreneurs and managers (e.g., Obschonka and Fisch, 2018; Obschonka et al., 2017), business angels (Block et al.,

2019), CEOs (Lee et al., 2017), and CMOs (Winkler et al., 2020).

Twitter is a social media site that allows users to post statements that are 140 characters or less in size and the most popular of these sites is Twitter (Fischer & Reuber, 2010). Twitter started to take off in terms of popularity in the first half of 2009 as a result of high-profile celebrity members and a mention on Oprah, and now it has become more main stream than other social media tools. Most companies should be on Twitter; it's easy, requires very little investment of time, and can quickly prove worthwhile in increased buzz, sales and consumer insight. Twitter can also be used to announce offers or events, promote new blog posts, or keep the readers in the know with links to important news stories. Twitter can be one way of staying on top of what the competitor is doing. The company can also show support to its Twitter-loving customers by subscribing to their tweets. Briefly, Twitter for businesses is a fast, easy, and free way to (1) stay on top of what the competitor is doing; (2) keep in touch with the own clients; (3) offer private discounts and sales announcements; (4) provide internal updates to team members and employees; (5) get leads on business opportunities, trends, and a jump on late-breaking news.

Twitter marketing is an idea, or plan that involves putting money and energy into creating a strategy that will drive traffic, engagement and sales for your business. It can be especially effective for brands that put focus on politics, blue collar industries, the social media industry, and Business-to-Business (B2B) sales. Another form of social media is microblogging, a concept commonly associated with Twitter, the most widely used microblogging site in the world (Burton, Dadich & Soboleva, 2013). Twitter allows users to post short text messages to individuals who have chosen to 'follow' the sender and followers are able to actively engage and forward or 'retweet' other's messages (Burton, Dadich & Soboleva, 2013). Microblogging is a form of digital communication that is on the rise that many businesses can use to their marketing advantage. Simply put, microblogs are sort of a combination of instant messages and blogs. It allows users to share small posts, such as a short sentence or an image, video, or link.

Launched in 2006, Twitter has 302 million daily users, who collectively send over 500 million tweets daily (Twitter, 2015). Of these active users, 80% use their mobile phone as a medium to tweet and/or retweet (Twitter, 2015). Alcohol and tobacco brands have made extensive use of Twitter (Burton & Soboleva, 2013). Alcohol companies have been known to make use of popular hashtags, and in so doing align their tweets with culturally popular and appealing customs and appeals, such as sport (Burton, Dadich & Soboleva, 2013). The use of popular hashtags by the alcohol industry is reminiscent of tobacco companies' attempts to associate consumer products with positive symbols and themes (Dadich, Burton & Soboleva, 2013).

With its potential for personalized communication with individuals who have chosen to follow an organization's Twitter feed, Twitter clearly increases the potential for interactive communication by organizations with their customers. Twitter can provide both types of interactivities: it allows both 'interpersonal interactivity' (through exchange of messages between an organization and individual, and by referencing others' messages) and also 'machine interactivity', for example through the use of embedded hyperlinks, which allow a tweet receiver to access extra information by clicking on links embedded within tweets. Organizational tweets can therefore be classified, as described in the following section, as reflecting different types of interactivities.

The research into interactivity in websites discussed above would suggest that tweets demonstrating higher levels of interactivity may lead to more positive recipient response. However, organizations may have different strategic aims in their use of Twitter; variations in the use of Twitter might also arise from variations in organizational type (for example, a service organization might use Twitter differently from an organization selling physical goods). There may also be differences in the use of Twitter in geographic markets with varying levels of Twitter usage.

While different organizations may therefore use different forms of communications, and may use varying forms at different times, the principle of strategic consistency would suggest that in the absence of market specific differences in strategy, organizations will use similar content mixes in their communications in different geographic markets. However there has been very limited academic work examining organizational use of Twitter, and no comparative studies across different geographic markets.

Use of Twitter is most prominent in the United States of America (US), with 62.1% of all Twitter users, with Australia, the fifth largest user of Twitter, with 2.2% of users (Cheng et al., 2009). As a result, in addition to classifying tweets according to their level of interactivity, the message contents of tweets from comparable organizations in different geographic markets are classified and compared. The implications for strategic use of Twitter as a marketing communications channel, are also considered.

➤ *Effectiveness of YouTube Marketing*

The process of promoting businesses products and services on YouTube's platform is done by uploading valuable videos on a company's YouTube channel or using YouTube ads. A good video marketing campaign is through video blogs using YouTube or simply called vlogs. Vlogs have been used for personal communication, especially by social media influencers. Billions of video hours are consumed by YouTube users each day. People spent so much time on YouTube that no cable network in the U.S. can compete with. Founded in early 2005, YouTube is a free service where subscribers can upload videos and share them with an audience of hundreds of millions (YouTube, 2015). Over one billion users visit YouTube each month with more than six billion hours of videos viewed (Barry et

al. 2015). Links to posted videos are easily shared through social media networks, allowing the effortless spread of video content (Freeman & Chapman, 2014). YouTube was originally designed for consumer-generated videos. The site has evolved rapidly, and given its reach and simplicity, has attracted manufacturers and marketers of consumer goods (Freeman & Chapman, 2014). Companies are also able to rely on users as distributors of promotions (Barry et al. 2015).

Research has suggested that YouTube has been used by the tobacco and alcohol industries to keep products favorably in the minds of current and potential consumers, and to reach vulnerable audience segments (Liang et al. 2015). YouTube is a popular site among adolescents, with 50% of teenagers citing YouTube as their favorite website (Barry et al. 2015). Further, 58% of generation X (1961-1979), 70% of generation Y (1980-1995) and 83% of generation Z (1995-2012) access YouTube on a monthly basis (Barry et al. 2015). YouTube is considered a covert medium of marketing labelled as 'below the line' marketing (Freeman & Chapman, 2014). Research has yet to explore the use of YouTube to position products desirably in the minds of consumers of any or all ages.

The unique characteristics of YouTube as a social-information platform also influence consumers' perceptions of information credibility. One of the unique characteristics of YouTube is the existence of comment sections. The comment sections accompanying YouTube videos provide viewers of the video a virtual venue to exchange ideas. These user comments exhibit the social function of YouTube. Through the exchange of ideas in the comment section, viewers of the video and the host of the channel interact with each other. Such interactions are very likely to shape people's opinions.

YouTube is used worldwide by two billion users per month (Roguski 2021), and in Poland by about 25.9 million (Kemp 2021), who watch more than four million videos every minute (Marr 2018), and the average time per session is about 40 min (Rutnik 2019). In order to register for the service, it is necessary to create a Google account. The beginnings of the platform date back to 2005. The service was founded by three IT specialists, but the following year it was purchased by Google. The significant interest from the investors contributed to the successful launch of the portal. A year after the first material was uploaded, the platform had 100 million views per day, with the number of videos increasing by 65,000 every day (Mohsin, 2022).

The classification of YouTube has been problematic for over a decade. Some scholars categorize it as a social medium (Aufar et al. 2020), citing the opinion of the site's creators, who were more concerned with positioning their product as a social network than a video storage website (Cyrek 2020b, p. 123). On the other hand, it is common knowledge that YouTube is not created as a social network platform but rather a video sharing platform (Cyrek 2020b, p. 124; Uryupina et al. 2014). This approach allows some researchers to describe YouTube as a social medium

(Wattenhofer et al. 2012). Burgess and Green (2011), on the other hand, pointed out that users of the platform do not make use of its social features, but mainly watch videos uploaded to it without regularly logging in and uploading videos. There is also its visual side, which is different from other social media. As Cyrek (2020) points out, it presents content through thumbnails of posted videos rather than profiles of creators and users (p. 124). A. Kavoori (2015) refers to YouTube's cultural aggregation because the site is "a totality where variously sized videos, commentaries, tools, tracking devices and logics of hierarchisation all combine into a dynamic seamless whole" (p. 24).

YouTube is a medium with a high degree of convergence, becoming a domain of media activity previously known for its press or radio forms. The platform offers not only the opportunity to create a channel and upload videos, but also to comment on them, share them or rate them. YouTube's marketing communication planning is also worth mentioning. Practical advice in this regard is offered by Google (2015), which emphasizes the need to design activities according to a strategic approach to building video content. This refers to the "Hero, Help and Hub" rule:

- Hero—creation of typical image-building, emotion-evoking and engaging content at key moments for marketing activities;
- Help—advisory content that can be used in practice, for example, answers to the service users' questions and searches;
- Hub—keeping the audience's attention, aimed at current subscribers, where the regularity of publication, and a unique character and style encouraging interaction with the channel owner's brand, are the most important factors.

Another noteworthy aspect is social TV, which results from the blending of traditional TV and social networks (Szews 2014, p. 67). There are two advantages of such a converging medium. For the viewer, it means the chance to reach and interact with journalists and media stars. For the medium, it provides increased analytical opportunities for ongoing activities and the implementation of marketing activities (Szews 2014, p. 68). Within the latter, YT can be used in various ways, for example, for presenting products and services, ways of assembling or applying them, and creating expert content (comments from company employees, answers to frequently asked questions, customer recommendations) (Kaczmarek-Sliwińska 2013, pp. 107–39). Moreover, YouTube channels can be accepted into the YouTube Partner Program (YPP), which means a chance for effective monetization. Being accepted into the partner programme means meeting the platform's requirements regarding public watch hours and subscribers. One of the necessary conditions is respecting copyrights and posting contents that do not violate legal regulations. Positively verified channels receive access to functions for earning advert revenue.

Nowadays, the strength of social advocacy is enhanced by the rise of digital media and social media. Previous studies have supported the notion that social influence or social advocacy influences one's opinions in a digital communication environment (Wu & Lin, 2017).

Wu & Lin (2017) examined online bandwagon effects and found that social advocacy significantly influenced consumers' evaluation on the quality of user-generated reviews. YouTube is a digital medium with a multimillion extensive and social functions (Zhao et al, 2015). Users on YouTube are likely to influence each other in various perspectives including individuals' perception of information credibility.

➤ *Social Media Impact on Sales and Marketing*

Social media sites do not only drive sales but also provide sources of marketing intelligence, especially when interactions between companies and social media users offer insights for product marketing. The term sales refer to all activities that lead to the selling of goods and services and marketing is the process of getting people interested in the goods and services being sold. Marketing departments are responsible for running campaigns to attract people to the business' brand, product, or service.

As social media proliferates, the roles of influencers are becoming increasingly diverse because digital technologies have increased the complexity of the customer environment. To match this complexity, micro business entities must consider not only existing criteria (i.e., sales, profits, growth rate, customer satisfaction, and loyalty) but also new marketing strategies and value propositions for customers (e.g., value, brand, relationship equity) (Kannan and Li, 2017). To address this situation, a new definition of social media marketing that considers the strategic level has been proposed. This definition describes social media marketing as an interdisciplinary and cross-functional process that uses social media to achieve organizational goals by creating value for stakeholders (Felix et al., 2017). Recent studies have also described the characteristics and narrative strategies of social media influencers (Harrigan et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2020).

Digital technologies have increased the complexity of the customer environment. Digital and social media marketing allows companies to achieve their sales and marketing objectives at a relatively low cost (Ajina, 2019). The decline of traditional communication channels and societal reliance on brick-and-mortar operations require businesses to seek best practices using digital and social media marketing strategies to retain and increase market share (Schultz and Peltier, 2012; Naylor et al., 2013). Companies need to consider not only existing marketing strategies (i.e., sales, profits, growth rate, customer satisfaction, and loyalty) but also new marketing strategies and value propositions for customers (e.g., value, brand, and relationship equity) (Kannan and Li, 2017). To adapt to these circumstances, a new definition of social media marketing has been proposed, according to which it is considered an interdisciplinary and cross-functional process

that uses social media (often in combination with other communication channels) to achieve organizational goals by creating value for stakeholders (Felix et al., 2017).

The new strategic definition of social media marketing encompasses an organization’s decisions about social media marketing scope (ranging from defenders to explorers), culture (ranging from conservatism to modernism), structure (ranging from hierarchies to networks), and governance (ranging from autocracy to anarchy). One new aspect of this process is social capital, which is the social, non-monetary value of consumers (community members) created by relational exchanges in the community. This involves behaviors such as advocacy, openness, and honesty (Sanz-Blas et al., 2021). From an organizational perspective, it has been argued that research on social media should move past the conventional dyadic view of the relationship between an online community and a firm and reconceptualize online users as a stakeholder ecosystem (Kapoor et al., 2018).

The vast multitude of social media sites available include Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube as the most popular sites for selling merchandise. With 1.65 billion monthly active users as of May 2016 (Zephoria Digital Marketing, 2016), Facebook is the market leader among

Social Networking Sites (SNS). However, social media users interact with brands on Instagram 58 times more often than they do on Facebook and 120 times more than on Twitter (O’Connor, 2014). Instagram has 400 million active monthly users who share more than 60 million photos every day (Leinbach-Reyhle, 2015). Fifty-three percent of adults between the ages of 18 and 29 years use Instagram (Patterson, 2015), making it arguably the world’s most powerful platform for brands (Zaryouni, 2015). Furthermore, posting an Instagram photo next to an item for sale boosts sales conversions by a factor of seven (Zaryouni, 2015).

In many cases, sales on social media sites depend on capabilities provided by businesses, which capture potential customers and facilitate sales of the retailer’s products through social media sites. The impacts that new buying channel and marketing method has on consumer decision-making processes in order to derive strategies that retailers can use to succeed in this new sales environment, as well as provide a model of retail strategies that boost purchases through social media platforms.

➤ *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

Fig 1 Areas of Conceptual Framework as Experience by Micro Business Entities in Social Media Marketing

The model shows the areas of exploration in the study: Micro business owners and managers lived experiences relative to the strong business marketing viability, interactive and promising social media platform and online customers behavior and feedback.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

The primary goals of the study is to investigate the lived experiences of micro business entities owners and managers on social media marketing and to explore the (1) effects of using social media platform to micro business entities sales and marketing; and (2) determine the social media platform which benefit the micro business entities to achieve their sales and marketing goals.

III. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

➤ *Subject*

The study focuses on managers and owners of the micro business entities in Baliwag, Bulacan. This study aims to identify the lived experiences of the micro business entities owners and managers in social media marketing.

Table 1 Business Profile of the Micro Enterprise Respondents

Respondent	Years of Active Business Experience	Business Name	Sector	Age	Owners Educational Background
1	3 years	E-Z Apparel Shop	Retail Industry	24	BSBA-MM
2	3 years	Nature Seeds and House	Retail Industry	25	BSBA-MM
3	2 years	Patty-D Apparels Co.	Retail Industry	26	BS Accountancy
4	3 years	Takoyakings	Foods Service	37	BSBA-FM
5	14 years	Winter Cool	Retail Industry	25	BSBA-MM
6	2 years	Prito. And Co	Foods Service	26	BSBA-MM
7	6 years	Katsumi Cuisine	Foods Service	43	BSCE
8	4 years	Jeff and Lily Branded Over run Shop	Retail Industry	27	BSBA
9	2 years	Cafe Beam	Foods Service	24	BSBA-MM
10	4 years	Clothing Co,	Retail Industry	26	BSBA-FM

As limitations, respondents in this study were selected from the profile of micro business in Baliwag, Bulacan as provided by Business and Permit Licensing Office Department (BPLOD). The micro business entities were selected based on the January 2021 list of registered business and the participating micro business entities came from three micro industry groups which comprised of six micro retail business entities; and four micro foods service business entities. The respondents will be selected through systematic sampling.

➤ *Instrument*

The researcher utilized a phenomenological method for the research. Phenomenology can be defined as an approach to research that seeks to describe the essence of phenomenon by exploring it from the perspective of those who have experienced it (Teherani et al, 2015). Phenomenology method is appropriate for this study since the purpose of this research is to gather data regarding the perspective of research respondents about the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004).

The research study used exploratory-ontological research question type. According Saldana (2013), ontological research problems are those intended to capture respondents' realities. As such, suggested coding methods utilized were attribute, emotion, in vivo, narrative, process, values and theming coding.

➤ *Data Collection and Procedure*

Since the study used phenomenological approach, data collection was done through interview in which the researcher asked questions to respondents through zoom video and g-meet conferencing. The interviews with the participants allowed for in-depth exploration of their professional experiences in social media marketing. The researcher used semi-structured question as guide. In semi-structures interviews, researcher prepared interview guides that includes a number of questions. Question may not be always be asked in the same order. Although the interview guide provides the same starting point for each semi-structured interviews, assuming common set of discussable topics, each interview will vary according to what was said by an individual respondent.

Semi-structured qualitative interviews were conducted via g-meet or zoom video recording as part of the interview setting to create the environment for the respondents (Qu & Dumay, 2011). Interview were transcribed verbatim, with the help of professional transcriptionist, before the data analysis begun. The researcher used ‘field notes’ to compliment with the recording. Sutton and Austin (2015) suggested field notes that allow the researcher to maintain and comment upon impressions, environmental contexts, behaviors, and non-verbal cues that may not be adequately captured in recording.

➤ *Data Analysis*

Analysis of qualitative research begins in the field, at the time of observation and interview. With the help of notes and recorded video procedure, analytic process was done. Below are the outlines of data analysis used as suggested by Schutt (Qualitative Data Analysis, 2019).

- Documentation of data and the process of data collection. Through the use of zoom recording, the original comments, observations were reconstructed and transcribed. According to Diamond (Schutt, 2019), in qualitative research, the basic data are those observations and conversations, the actual words of people used in the conversation. Included in the documentation is the contact summary that will be used to track the sessions as suggested by Miles and Huberman (Miles & Huberman, 1994).
- Organization/Categorization of data into concepts. The researcher used open coding by identifying and refinement of important concepts through iterative process. Encyclopedia of Case Study Research defined iterative process as systematic, repetitive and recursive process in qualitative data analysis. It involves a sequence task carried out in exactly the same manner multiple times. It provides a deepening understanding of research data and brings a standard of reliability to research. Iterative process in this study was observed in same guide questions that were asked to the respondents. (Mills, Dupero & Wiebe, 2012). By use of Microsoft Word, each word, phrase, sentences, and paragraph was highlighted.
- Connection of the data to show how one concept may influence another. Connecting the data through examining the relationships was done through analytical process. This is said to be the centerpiece of analytical activity.
- Corroboration/Legitimization, by evaluating alternative explanations. Disconfirming evidence, and searching for negative cases. This data analysis stage helped the researcher to authenticate the conclusion. Schutt (2019) suggested some internal guide thematic questions for the researcher in authenticating the conclusion such as:

how credible is the informant, were statements made in response to the researchers’ questions, or where they spontaneous; how does the presence or absence of the researcher participants influence the action and their statement.

- Representing the account (reporting the findings). The findings from this research study were supported by informative and honest account including how the researcher interact with the respondents reporting of possible problems that were encounter and how they were solved. The researcher tried to display, in the words of Altheide and Johnson (1994), “real sensitivity to how a social situation or process is interpreted from particular background and set of values and not simply based on situation itself”.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

To ensure that ethical guidelines are followed, participants must be given informed guidelines, the risk to the participants should be minimized, and appropriate methodological procedures should be followed (Wester, 2011). Ethical Research or Ethics in research, which result in the protection of human participants, are recognized both by government and professional regulations (Stiles, Epstein, Poythress, & Edens, 2012).

Voluntary consent and confirmation that the participants are willing to participate should be included in the ethical guidelines (Harcourt, & Sargeant, 2011). All participants in the study were required to agree to a consent form and the researcher informed the participants about the description of the background and purpose of the study. The participants were given ample time for the to withdraw from the study at any point. Personal data collected from the participants were treated confidentially. The participants were provided with a copy of the consent form and the transcripts of the study at its conclusion.

A copy of the consent form was provided and the participants did not receive any monetary incentive for participating in the study and were provided the ability to withdraw from the study without penalty (Sachs, 2011). The consent forms, as well as the files, transcripts, and recordings from the research, are stored on a private external hard drive with utmost confidentiality to ensure the protection of the rights of the participants.

The researcher likewise, predicated on an ideal of how one should treat others and how society should be organized and function. The ethic of reciprocity or —Golden Rule is applied “Do unto others as you would have done unto you” (Luke 6:31). The researcher, therefore, adhered to a Christian worldview in order to establish the principles and standards of conduct. The values by which one frames his philosophy determines both the efficacy and legitimacy of the researcher.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interviews with the researcher were transcribed verbatim and were analyzed fully in order to look for significant statements, formulate their meanings and classify them accordingly. Subsequently, all the significant information gathered from the data were analyzed to form key words and phrases that fell into emergence themes.

Table 2 Themes Generated from the Interview Data

Theme 1. Strong Business and Marketing Viability
Subtheme 1: Emerging Customer Interpenetration
Subtheme 2: Top Social Media Marketing Platform
Subtheme 3: Influence of Liking, Sharing and Tagging
Theme 2. Interactive and Promising Platform Channel
Subtheme 1: Traditional and Unconventional Marketing Comparability
Subtheme 2: Leverage Digital Marketing Stratagems
Subtheme 3: Realizable Customers Reach
Subtheme 4: Insistent Sales Appreciation
Theme 3. Online Customers Behavior and Feedback
Subtheme 1: Positive feedback and comments
Subtheme 2: Negative feedback and comments
Subtheme 3: Downside of online selling

Table 2 provides the lived experience of micro business entities owners and managers categorized into different themes and subthemes generated based on the experiences of key respondents. This resulted from several reiterations of verbatim transcription, open coding and labeling of respondents sharing, axial categorization and the thematic analysis process. The researcher ensured that the data was presented as objectively as possible based on both explicit and implicit intention of respondents. The researcher further applied bracketing, Tufford and Newman (2010) defined bracketing as a method used by some researchers to mitigate the potential deleterious effects of unacknowledged preconception related to the research and thereby to increase the rigor of the project.

Themes 1, 2, and 3 were responses to the main statement of the problem, “What are the effects of using social media platform to micro business entities sales and marketing?” Themes were based on the different lived experiences by respondents.

➤ *Theme 1. Strong Business and Marketing Viability*

In the first theme, participants described their social media marketing experience in different ways. Several subthemes emerged relating to the answers of the participants. These includes emerging customer

interpenetration, top social media marketing platform and influence of liking, sharing and tagging.

The interview questions that were asked (see Appendix) were probing questions regarding the social media marketing experiences of micro business owners. They were asked to describe their business experience with the use of social media and the types of social media marketing platform they use; the influence of liking, sharing and tagging as well as the effects of employing several social media platforms to their business sales and marketing.

➤ *Subtheme 1. Emerging Customer Interpenetration*

There are ten respondents in this study, seven respondents are female and three respondents are male. Respondents’ age ranges from 24 to 43 years old. Eight of them are graduates of Business Administration; one is a graduate of a BS in Accountancy; and one BS in Civil Engineering.

Respondents came from different micro business entities; the retail and wholesale business, and the micro foods service business partaking two years to five years of business operation experience. All of the respondents have utilized the use of social media platform as their sales and marketing channel.

Table 3 Respondent 7

G1388	Respondent 7	Malakas ang ano... malakas ang ano ng social media marketing uhm... if you're starting a business... kasi ako nag-start ako I was lucky when I opened Junction 88 back in 2016, the first day was full packed. Nag-post lang ako non na mag-oopen kami, nagboost sa Facebook. And also the Katsumi, when I opened last year, I started with takeout, yun lang. I have a business page tapos naglagay ako ng restaurant. Sabi ko soft opening this day, pero that day we opened, it's also full packed then. So, it really helps a lot na yung dati na madadaan lang ng tao na, “Uy, meron pa lang bagong bukas dyan.” Pero ngayon, social media talaga, it change the ano... the way kung pano mo i-market ang iyong business.
G1389		
G1390		
G1391		
G1392		
G1393		
G1394		
G1395		
G1396		
G1397		
G1398		
G1399		

G1400		
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The market viability as described by Respondent 7 who is in foods service business - Line G1394 to G1397, state that his business was strongly boosted when he posted it on Facebook during his business soft opening. The turn-out of the customers was surprisingly high. Respondent 7 also added that the use of social media can actually influence how the business market its product expressed in Line G1398 to G1400.

Table 4 Respondent 1

A47 A48 A49 A50 A51 A52 A53 A54 A55 A56	Respondent 1	Uhhh, Facebook po kase uhhh... mayron po kasing option don na kung i-boost mo yung product kase pag binoost mo po siya mas maraming marreach yung post kaya mas marami po yung chance na makakuha tayo ng buyer or yung nmga taong magiging interested sa products ganun po. Pero, more on sa IG po kasi mas maganda na magbabayad ka talaga ng ads para sila na mismo yung magbboost ng post mo kase pag ikaw lang at walang tulong ng ads kase mahirap kase konti lang yung makakakita ng products or depende po yun kung pano mo siya ipopromote.
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Table 5 Respondent 2

B163 B164 B165 B166 B167	Respondent 2	First, sir uhh... ginamit naming yung social media marketing to reach out customers and also po yun na din po yung communication namin6g with the suppliers and yung aming mga mananahi. So, doon po kami nag-eexchange ng messages, information and transactions po.
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Boosting your business through Facebook can penetratingly reach the buyers and increase the chance of attracting customers to purchase online, as stated by Respondent 1 who is in retail of clothing business, Line A47 to A51. As cited by Grabowicz (2014), social media users facilitate interactivity and engagement in business communication. As what Respondent 2, who is in retail business of nature seeds, she stressed out that using Facebook can significantly increase customers reach and they used it as a medium of business communication with their suppliers in exchanging central messages, information and transaction.

Table 6 Respondent 6

F1136 F1137 F1138 F1139 F1140 F1141 F1142 F1143 F1144 F1145 F1146 F1147 F1148 F1149 F1150 F1151 F1152 F1153 F1154 F1155 F1156 F1157 F1158 F1159 F1160	Respondent 6	Ano, sir eh.. way back then po, parang limited lang po talaga yung audience mo. For example, kapitbahay, kakilala, kamag-anak, classmate before, circle of friends, yung lang yung magiging consumers mo or customers mo pagka-wala talagang physical store na nasa magandang location. Ngayon sir, naisip ko, bakit ko kinukulong ko yung Negosyo ko sa loob lang ng bahay naman or compound naming kung pwede namang ipagsigawan na mas marami pang audience na makakita dun sa product na binebenta ko or dun sa food business na meron ako. That’s why, ayon pinush ko po agad or pinursue ko po agad na ma-boost yung sales ko via social media na nag-post po ako one time about my new products na dati na pagka-nagluluto ng panibagong produkto ang nakakaalam lang niyan, regular customer ko na po eh. Pero, nung nagpunta po ako ng Social Media, nag-create ako ng new product innovation, nung pinost ko po iyon sa social media, nagkaroon ng maraming reach and engagement sa mga customers na dati hindi ko naman tina-target. Ibig sabihin po, yung mismong data na nanggaling from my social media sites yung mismong gumalaw para sa business ko. Hindi po ako nagpaka-pagod na mag-ikot ikot at maglako pa para magbenta ng aking products pero because of Facebook eh mas maraming nakakita dun sa negosyong binebenta ko. Mas marami rin pong consumers and naging self-generation kaya mas Malaki po ang kita nung panahon na yon.
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Facebook visibility contributes to the rising number of target customers which leads to composite profit according to Respondent 6, who is in foods service business as expressed in Line F1157 to F1160. He emphasized pushing and pursuing social media utilization by posting his new products to reach greater number of audience and customer engagement.

The analytics in the social media sites speak or present of how business reaches consumer as implied in the line F1154 to F11555.

Table 7 Respondent 4

D734 D735 D736 D737	Respondent 4	Social media is malaki ang hatak sa tao yung ano niya yung uhmm... benefits niya from sales to promotion. Yung iba hindi sila kumakain ng Takoyaki pero nung nakita nila sa FB parang ang sarap, even the product pictures, they'll try it.
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The utilization of social media marketing has significance to Respondent 4 who is in foods service business, probing that people is much attracted, when they see the products posted in Facebook it also has a great benefit in their sales and promotions. She also mentioned that those who do not eat Takoyaki before, suddenly wanted to try the product upon seeing the post in Facebook.

According to Wagner et al. (2019), the size and the geographic location of a business nowadays do not matter in online business because globalization has triggered the advancement of technology, which enforces many companies to use digital business and current trend in social media marketing to fulfill the needs of internationalization and competitive advantage in emerging markets.

➤ *Subtheme 2. Top Social Media Marketing Platform*

One of the most common experiences among respondents is the use of more sophisticated marketing platform like Facebook as their marketplace, Facebook business page, live selling, private groups for buy and sell in different geographical location.

Respondents also use their Facebook page to link with their Shopee account for their product checkouts as stated in line H1590 to H1603. Whereas, Respondent 3 also stated that they use Facebook and Instagram as their business marketing platforms in line C394.

Respondent 5, who is in retail business, in Line E902 to E903, uses Facebook and Google as their marketing network and Respondent 2, who is in retail of clothing business -- line B181 to B183, expressed the use of Facebook page and Facebook marketplace.

Respondent 1, a retailer of clothing, in Line A43, also uses Facebook and Instagram and for the Respondent 10 who is in retail of clothes business; in Line J1963, uses Facebook for everyday posting. Respondent 4, who is foods service business, also uses Facebook as expressed in line D742; and Respondent 7, who is in foods service business, in line G1416 reliably, uses Facebook and he also mentioned that most of the people are ordering through Messenger or Facebook Page.

Table 8 Respondent 8

H1590 H1591 H1592 H1593 H1594 H1595 H1596 H1597 H1598 H1599 H1600 H1601 H1602 H1603	Respondent 8	Uhh.. ang ginagamit po naming is uhh... Facebook, Marketplace ni Facebook, uh... created Private Group like Baliuag Buy and Sell, Luzon, Visayas, Mindanao Buy and Sell then, we also created account in Shopee. We have Shopee Checkout po. Then, sa Shopee po, pwede rin kami mag-live then pwede rin mag-order sa Shopee yung mga customer naming from Mindanao kasi mas maliit po yung SF na tinatawag or yung Shipping Fee sa Shopee compared sa direct shipment naming sa J&T. Yun po yung mga advantages kapag malayo yung location tapos ipapa-shopee checkout. Then may FB Page din po kami na ginagamit, dun po naming pinopost yung mga available stocks po naming, pricelist po ng mga item then yung mga sample picture ng mga items na pwedeng mabili po sa amin.
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Table 9 Respondent 3

C392 C393	Researcher	Ahh, okay po. Uhm, ma'am, nabanggit niyo po Youtube, tama po ba?
C394	Respondent 3	Uhm... Facebook and Instagram.

Table 10 Respondent 5

E902 E903	Respondent 5	Sa ngayon, ang ginagamit naming is Facebook and Google. Pero, we're planning din... inaayos namin yung sa website.
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Table 11 Respondent 2

B177 B178 B179 B180	Researcher	Okay, thank you ma'am. Ma'am, isa pa po, uhm.. maaari ko po bang malaman kung anong type ng social media marketing platform ang ginagamit ninyo para sa inyong produkto na ino-offer sa marketplace?
B181 B182 B183	Respondent 2	Ginagamit naming sir is uhh... Facebook, Facebook Page, Marketplace sa Facebook and also, pinasok na rin po naming ang Shopee.

Table 12 Respondent 1

A41 A42	Researcher	Ahh okay. So, ano pong social media platforms po ang gamit niyo?
A43	Respondent 1	Uhm, Facebook and IG.

Table 13 Respondent 10

J1963 J1964 J1965 J1966 J1967 J1968 J1969 J1970 J1971 J1972 J1973 J1974	Respondent 10	Sakin... siguro talagang everyday posting sa Facebook, personal account then sa page. Tapos uhm... aside from that, ano ba... uhm... kasi meron din akong marketer, parang advertiser ng ano ko... ng page parang ganon. May hinire akong tao na talagang kilala siya sa mga ano... ahmm parang Tiktok sensation, Youtuber siya so, kinuha ko siya, so naging ano ko siya... naging malakas ako din dahil sa kanya kasi once na shinare niya yung post ko sa page niya or personal account niya, dun din ako nakikilala. Siguro para sakin ang naging ano ko dito talagang nag-laan ako ng funds para doon sa kinuha kong advertiser ganon. Parang ganon.yes po...
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Table 14 Respondent 4

D742 D743 D744 D745 D746 D747 D748 D749	Respondent 4	Actually, we have Facebook Page lang. Sa marketplace kasi, uhh... minsan nagkaron.. uh... gumamit kami niyan pero nagkaron kami ng problema kasi from Baliwag, merong nagpapadeliver sa Meycauayan. So, sabi ko, mag-stick na lang kami sa page na lang. Hanggang sa, si Takoyakings Baliuag nagkaron na ng anak na si Takoyakings Bustos and then marami ring umo-order dito Tangos at food park sa Sullivan, naglagay na rin kami ng isa. So, nanganganak siya.
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Table 15 Respondent 7

G1412 G1413 G1415	Researcher	Sir, pwede ko po bang malaman, usually po kasi marami tayong social media types? Ano po yung mga social media platform na ginagamit niyo sa ngayon?
G1416	Respondent 7	For now, I only use Facebook...
G1453 G1454	Respondent 7	Yes, because most of the people are ordering through Messenger or Facebook Page.

It has been observed that Facebook is the most social media marketing platform used by the respondents apart from Instagram, YouTube and Google. According to Freeman et al. (2014), Facebook is the most popular for social networking site in the world.

Overall, the lived experiences of SME's social media marketing users are parallel to the Facebook claim that it was able to generate more than 5.4\$ billion from advertising with growing percent up to 58%. Furthermore, Facebook revenue from advertising has grown by 59 % during the past year to over \$5.4 billion in 2014 (Facebook, 2014), which is evidence to the evolving shift from traditional media advertising to digital interactive media advertising by many business organizations. However, such growing interest

could be constituted to the high level of attractiveness and interactivity existing in social media platforms (Swani et al., 2016; Wu, 2016).

➤ *Subtheme 3: Influence of Liking, Sharing and Tagging*

Another subtheme that emerged from the interview was the influence of social media likes, shares and tags. People engage in social media communication on Facebook via three behaviors—like, shares, and tags. Facebook uses an algorithm that gives different weight to each behavior to determine what to show in user's screen, suggesting that the strategic implication of each behavior may differ from the other.

The respondents share their lived experiences is the implications of like, share and tag with respects to their

product endorsement and how it likely to influence their business using digital marketing.

Table 16 Respondent 4

D695 D696 D697 D698 D699 D700 D701 D702	Respondent 4	Uh huh. Kasi pag ang target mo lang kasi is yung mga relatives mo, yung mga kakilala mo, maliit yung network mo eh. But when you it on social media, doon dumadami kasi everyone can see it eh. Pag tinag mo yung friends mo, may friends sila, yung friends nila, may friends pa. So, ma-ccurious sila kung ano ba yung lasa ng Takoyakings na yun. At ngayon meron na kaming 4,000 likes sa page. Medyo blessed talaga.
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According to Respondent 4, who is in foods service business, in line D695 to D702, she mentions that if the target market is comprised only of the relatives, and acquaintances, your network is insignificantly small. Social media can significantly expand the target market. It creates webs of networks beyond direct contacts. It prompts curiosity for new products. This is evident with the business of one respondent, Takoyakings, which currently has already 4,000 likes in its Facebook page.

Table 17 Respondent 9

I1765 I1766 I1767 I1768 I1769 I1770 I1771 I1772 I1773 I1774 I1775	Respondent 9	Actually, malaking bagay po siya eh... malaking tulong kasi yung mga traditional marketing like yung flyers ay hindi na po masyado nag-wwork especially with this type of business. Usually lahat po makikita sa social media kasi parang naging word of mouth din siya, for example, meron ako isang customer na nagpost and comment, makikita ng ibang potential customers na, "Uy, saan yan?" And also, ito na rin yung nagiging way ko para ma-boost yung mga posts ko kasi syempre, the audience will tend to like, comment and also even share our post, minsan i-shshare nila yun and they will tag their friends. Ayun ganon po.
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As perceived by the Respondent 9, who is in foods service business, in line I1768 to 1769, social media perceptibility is like a word of mouth that can easily spread and reach the target customers, particularly if the customers give comment that can be seen by other potential customer online. As cited by the respondent, the comment "Uy, saan yan?" in Line I1771, extremely influences the intensity to boost the posting of the business product by liking, sharing, commenting and tagging of friends stated in Line I1772 to I1775.

Table 18 Respondent 10

J1984 J1985 J1986 J1987 J1988 J1989 J1990 J1991	Respondent 10	Yes...oo, yes... kasi, kagaya ko, buyer din ako, buyer din ako before ako naging online seller, buyer din talaga ko ng mga ukay. So, talgang pag may nag-share na mga friends ko ng nag-llive sell tapos talagang nakikita ko andaming viewers, ang daming nag-cocomments so talagang mahihikayat ka din na panoorin. So talagang malaki ang naitutulong ng mga tags, likes, shares and comments pag pinupush yung ganong Gawain nila.
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Respondent 10 who is in retail clothes business, in Lines J1987 to J1991, shared her experience with Facebook live selling, that having so many viewers comments, tags, likers and sharers is indeed a great help to encourage and boost more people to become attracted to the product online.

Table 19 Respondent 7

G1418 G1419 G1420 G1421 G1422	Respondent 7	It depends kasi na-notice ko sa Bulacan, most likely ay... yung type ng business ko ay I will get my clients from Facebook share and tags. For the Sashimi in Manila, I get them in Instagram ads. So it depends on the... sa region... hindi ko alam kung bakit ganon eh.
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Respondent 7 who is in foods service business, in line G1419 to G1420, most likely get his customers through the strong influence of Facebook sharing and tagging.

➤ *Theme 2. Interactive and Promising Platform Channel*

In modern business, social media marketing is largely considered as a promising platform to conduct the promotional activities as to effectively communicate with the wide range of targeted customers (Popp & Woratschek, 2016). This theme presents the effects of using the traditional marketing approach and unconventional methods to sales and marketing of selected micro business entities. The researcher also exhibits the most influential sources of marketing for reaching a greater audience and growing business and the way how the emergence of social media changes the way of marketers and customers interaction.

➤ *Subtheme 1. Traditional and Unconventional Marketing Comparability*

The use of traditional and unconventional marketing approach has a vast influence to micro business entities owners as perceived by the respondents of this study. However, the theme presents the comparability of two different methods of marketing to further give the reader an immense knowledge concerning the perceived effects of

both traditional and unconventional marketing to micro business entities sales.

According to Godin (2014), the advertising and promotion of a product and services in social media diverges from the traditional product and service marketing because social media advertising is an inordinate entity that works along a continuum that is ever-evolving.

The immersive experience using traditional and unconventional marketing has perceived great benefits specifically for the ever-growing needs of micro business entities sales and marketing. However, the unprecedented shift from traditional to modern marketing plays a vital role for the development of business strategy on sales and marketing performance.

For the Respondent 3, who is in retail business of clothing, there is a big difference between organic selling and digital selling. He cited that organic selling can generate 20 orders while digitalselling using Facebook can possibly produce 100 orders.

Table 20 Respondent 3

C363 C364 C365 C366 C367 C368	Respondent 3	Uhh, of course, it is more.. ahh..malaki talaga yung dipirensya like sa sales lang, like for example, if you're just going base on organic selling, uhm.. like for example, if we're going to rate it 20 orders lang but of course if you're going to have a pool like FB ads marketing it can come up to a hundred of orders.
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Respondent 7, who is in foods service business, explains that there is a big difference of placing ads in social media. He cited that if he did not place an ad in social media, his client will only be his regular clients alone but unlike putting the ads online, he will be able to have additional clients from different locations. He reiterated that putting ads online can really help the business, stated in Line G1405 to G1411.

Table 21 Respondent 7

G1405 G1406 G1407 G1408 G1409 G1410 G1411	Respondent 7	There is. Malaki din ang ano... kasi... let's say in Manila, I have an online store there which is for steak. Pag hindi ako nag-advertise... let's say, I only have a website, pero hindi ako nag-place ng ads, ang client mo lang talaga will be your regular clients. Pag naglagay ka ng ads, you'll see different clients all the way... minsan Parañaque, Cavite, Antipolo so, iba pa rin talaga yung pag naglagay ka ng ano... ng ads.
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The traditional marketing using flyers according to Respondent 9, is not that effective with her type of business stated in Line I1766 to I1767. She explains that all should be seen social media has fa greater reach and works like the word of mouth as stated in Line I1768 to I1769. She also added the impact of customer posts and comments that can really influence the power for boosting potential customers particularly the audience likes, shares, comments and tags in Line I1770 to I1772.

Table 22 Respondent 9

I1765 I1766 I1767 I1768 I1769 I1770 I1771 I1772 I1773 I1774	Respondent 9	Actually, malaking bagay po siya eh... malaking tulong kasi yung mga traditional marketing like yung flyers ay hindi na po masyado nag-wwork especially with this type of business. Usually lahat po makikita sa social media kasi parang naging word of mouth din siya, for example, meron ako isang customer na nagpost and comment, makikita ng ibang potential customers na, "Uy, saan yan?" And also, ito na rin yung nagiging way ko para ma-boost yung mga posts ko kasi syempre, the audience will tend to like, comment and also even share our post, minsan i-shshare nila yun and they will tag their friends. Ayun ganon po.
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I1775		
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Based on the answer given by Respondent 10, who is in retail of clothing business, she mentions that using flyers in traditional marketing is indeed rigorous as stated in Line J2034 to J2035. She described that online selling takes a little effort since products just need to display or modelled, as stated in Line J2039 to J2041. Selling beauty products online is also easier as stated in Line J2039 to J2041. Further, she repeated that, traditional marketing approach is more laborious compared to social media way of marketing stated in Line J2041 to J2043.

Table 23 Respondent 10

J2034 J2035 J2036 J2037 J2038 J2039 J2040 J2041 J2042 J2043	Respondent 10	Ahh, oo. Para saakin kasi, kagaya non... mag-flyers ka pa, masyadong matrabaho ang traditional kasi kung sa social media, mag-live ka lang tapos ipapakita mo lang, kahit nga hindi ka magbenta, papakita mo lang yung daily offers mo. Laking help sa tulad ko, on-line nagtitinda ako ng beauty products, yung iba nag-live lang pero ang pinapakita lang nila is kung pano nila ina-apply yung mga beauty products, ganon lang. So, in that way, nakakapag-advertise na sila without having some paperworks. Hmm... so, mas matrabaho ang traditional para saakin compared sa social media na way.
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Common perceptions among respondents with respects to their sales performance is being raised. Respondent 1, who is in retail of clothing business, also mentioned the low sales performance because of limited viability. Furthermore, with the utilization of Facebook and Instagram, the reliability of the product is established because of customers engagement through testimonials, as stated in Line A67 to A72.

Table 24 Respondent 1

A67 A68 A69 A70 A71 A72	Respondent 1	Uhm... nung nakaraan po kase parang mas mababa yung sale kase konti lang nakakareach pero ngayon okay na kase more on boosting talaga sa social media like Facebook and IG kaya malaki yung tulong niya para mas magkaroon ng foundation yung shop kase maraing nagtiwala kase mas marami nang tao na nagpatunay.
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Respondent 4, who is in foods service business, essentially explains the difference of using traditional and modern marketing approach. She further emphasizes that their sales are weak without using Facebook. The influence of Facebook use is evident on the significant increase of orders from far places like Pulilan, San Rafael and Sto. Cristo. Thus, it resulted to increased product sales and visibility.

Table 25 Respondent 4

D686 D687 D688 D689 D690 D691 D692	Respondent 4	Actually, malaki yung difference kasi mahina yung sales mo... although, umaakyat siya pero hindi ganon ka-progressive. Iba ang may social media... nung nalagay na naming siya sa Facebook, we have orders na galing sa ibang lugar like Pulilan, hindi lang basta sa Sto. Cristo, kundi meron na rin kami sa San Rafael so, nag-spread out siya, mas mabilis tumaas yung sales.
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➤ *Subtheme 2. Leverage Digital Marketing Stratagems*

The social media marketing appeals to influence most business publicity through the way how business consumers view themselves and how buying a certain product can prove to be beneficial and effective (Sharmilee,2016). The use of different digital marketing platforms to leverage consumer numbers seems to be an unheralded strategy to be more attractive to the customers to develop a product-centric groups in such a way that ties the sellers and customers

engagement. According to Kissane, (2016) social media is the marketing avenue for businesses seeking to expand their reach online, attract new customers, and leverage more of their traffic into sales.

For the Respondent 8, who is in retail clothing business, the utilization of social media is a big factor for their sales and in the online world, stated in Line H1530 to H1532.

Table 26 Respondent 8

H1530 H1531 H1532	Respondent 8	Yes po. Bale, yan po yung isang malaking factor... napakalaking factor na nagbigay po sa amin ng mas malaking sales, yung social media at saka yung online world.
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Social media marketing is very crucial, especially to micro and small medium enterprises. It is cost effective and cheaper mechanism to influence people as target consumers. Apparently, the relevance of using social media for the business is also highlighted by the Respondent 6, although, his business is not that large.

Table 27 Respondent 6

F1083 F1084 F1085 F1086 F1087 F1088 F1089 F1090 F1091	Respondent 6	Sir, social media marketing is a very essential tool lalo na sa mga micro small and medium enterprise dahil mas cost effective po eh... napakamura pero... the reach na nakukuha natin for.. for the engagement den, for those people or target consumers natin, eh hamak na mas malaki instead of using the traditional way of marketing our product. Kaya po, napakahalaga po talaga ng social media marketing para sa mga business na katulad nung sa akin na hindi naman ganon kalakihan.
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According to Respondent 2 who is in nature seeds retail business, social media marketing basically assists his business in a way of exchanging information that helps to increase sales generation. Introducing business, new product, new item can visibly give a customer a teaser specifically in the form of videos and advertisement in social media.

Table 28 Respondent 2

B169 B170 B171 B172 B173 B174 B175 B176	Respondent 2	Sobrang laking tulong sir, actually. Kasi po ang social media marketing hindi lang po siya uhh... nagiging way of exchange information, nagiging daan din po siya sir para maging mas tumaas yung sales niyo kasi diba business is more about profit diba po? So, in introducing your business, your new product, your new item, parang nagbibigay ka sa kanila ng teaser in a way na gumagawa ka ng video, gumagawa ka ng advertisement using social media po.
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Respondent 3, who is in retail of apparel business, truly thinks that social media marketing is more effective nowadays, especially that majority of the youth are preoccupied with their Facebook account. She really finds Facebook effective and more convenient especially in this pandemic situation. She also added the benefits, that even at home, the expediency of selling online is cost effective and more efficient.

Further, it is highly suggested by the Respondent 3 to consider the use of Facebook ads to expand in marketing particularly in expanding the business.

Table 29 Respondent 3

C329 C330 C331 C332 C333 C334 C335 C336 C337 C338	Respondent 3	Uhm.. I really do think that social media marketing is more effective nowadays especially most of the times youths are. you know.. really engaged to their Facebook account and I really find it effective and it is more convenient to us because uhm.. since pandemic uhm.. we do need to...you know.. rent a place where in we establish a business and we could just sell online and just be in the house. So, mas less yung cost and also mas efficient to us because we don't need to go somewhere else to sell our items. So, I think it is more efficient.
C352 C353 C354 C355 C356 C357 C358 C359		Uhm.. at first, hinde. Uhm.. for our first brand uhm.. normally kasi pag nagsimula 'yan sa mga friends lang, sa dami ng friends, sila yung mga uinang oorder until makilala within the area and of course dadating yung time na yan na konti na yung magiging order and that is the time na you're going to expand your marketing and doon macoconsider yung FB ads and marketing and yon.. uhm.. highly suggested yon especially if you really want to expand your business.

The Respondent 4, who is in foods service business, basically uses Facebook believing that majority of the people are using it including children. It reaches diverse profile of users. Hence, the exposure of the product extends to all types of account holders.

Table 30 Respondent 4

D677 D678 D679 D680	Respondent 4	Kasi si Facebook lahat meron eh. Even bata, so hindi siya nakikita ng mayayaman lang, ng mga low level lang, kundi lahat may Facebook. kumbaga hindi siya namimili lang ng market niya eh everyone can see Takoyakings in Facebook.
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Facebook contributes to the increase in sales as per Respondent 7, who is in foods service business, especially during the pandemic situation wherein most of the transaction are done through online like online orders of foods & other essentials.

Table 31 Respondent 7

G1457 G1458 G1459 G1460	Respondent 7	For its contribution, uhm... I think it really boost our sales kase... lalo na ngayong pandemic where most of the transactions are just happening online, people are most likely do online orders for their food and even other essentials.
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➤ *Subtheme 3. Realizable Customers Reach*

According to Rouse (2019), the goal of social media marketing is to produce content that users will share with their social network to help a company increase product exposure and broaden customer reach.

Respondent ,9 who is in retail of branded clothes business anticipated that 80% of her customers is mostly from social media exposure when they got featured in preview magazine online. Online sharing attracts more customers who also help on supporting the product through repeated purchase orders.

Table 32 Respondent 9

I1791 I1792 I1793 I1794 I1795 I1796 I1797	Respondent 9	Yes. Yes po. Mostly, actually, mga 80% talaga ng customers ko Nakita nila yung café sa social media. Kasi on our first month, we got featured sa preview magazine online and yon nagsimula na pong magshare yung mga tao na may bago po palang café dito so, maraming ang-try, maraming pumunta, at naging repeat customers naman po sila. And, I'm glad naman po na mostly sa social media talga nila nakikita.
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Another experience encountered by Respondent 5, who is in retail business of clothes, considerably explains the increase in sales over online sales and promotions. Through the use of Facebook posting, their customers are forced to browse online and inquire for sale items that do not only help in expansion but also in the increase of sales.

Table 33 Respondent 5

E915 E916 E917 E918 E919 E920	Respondent 5	Ayon nga kumbaga. Nag-iincrease naman kami ng sales kapag may promotions kami, mga sales ganon, ppost din naming sa FB, syempre, yung mga customer ngayon pag nakakakita ng sale, mag-iinquire sila, minsan, sag anon kami nakakakuha ng sale. So, it helps sa sales din hindi lang sa expansion.
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For Respondent 2, who is in retail of nature seeds business, social media marketing is simply used for business to broaden customer reach and exposure. Utilizing such, is more effective especially this pandemic situation that prefer to purchase online at the comfort of their home. Business owners maximize the use of different platform especially small business owner as it is documented as the best marketing tools for 2021.

Table 34 Respondent 2

B149 B150 B151 B152 B153 B154 B155 B156 B157	Respondent 2	Ahh. For me, sir, ang social media marketing is uhh.. anon a siya ngayon eh... ginagamit na siya for business para mas mapalawig pa yung pagreach out natin sa ating mga customer and also mas effective siya ngayon since nagkaron tayo ng pandemic and mahirap po tayong lumabas so, nagina ano siya ngayon sir. Bale gamitin siya ngayong ng mga business owners specially po yung mga small business owner like us na gamitin kasi yun po yung parang best marketing tools for today, 2021 po.
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The social media provides a rapid and easy way to widen customer connections with people across the region. It really helps for easy market penetration, for product introduction to give awareness and exposure to the target customers. Facebook can really help their business specifically when they incorporate the use of Facebook as marketing tools which relatively augmented to 60% of their sales.

Table 35 Respondent 7

G1462	Respondent 7	So, the social media... uhm... provides us a quick and easy way to widen our connections with people across the region. And sa tingin ko, nakakatulong siya especially sa market penetration so that you will uhh... have the chance to introduce your products and give insights to my target customers about what I am offering. Let's take this as an example, before when... hindi pa ko gumagamit ng social media especially the Facebook, it is really hard for me to gather orders. Why? It's mainly because my product hasn't been introduced to the market yet. But guess what, the moment that we incorporated social media as our marketing tool, our sales went up like almost 60%. And that is really how social media works.
G1463		
G1464		
G1465		
G1466		
G1467		
G1468		
G1469		
G1470		
G1471		
G1472		
G1473		
G1474		

Face to face selling in just nearby places can only capture small market and it has only a minimal and limited number of sales. When they applied and used online marketing, a greater number of customers from Visayas and Mindanao were reached and not just their customers from Bulacan. Presently, they are the supplier to a nearby province in Tarlac, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga and even in National Capital Manila.

➤ *Subtheme 4: Insistent Sales and Marketing Appreciation*

Respondent 6 who is in foods service business, Line F1221 to F1237 shared that previous average monthly earning without the use of social media is onlu P6,000. The use of social media in advertising and selling of products substantially increased the monthly income to P24,000.

Table 36 Respondent 6

F1221	Respondent 6	Yes, sir. Siguro, sir let's go back na lang into numbers, sir. Nung panahon na wala pa kong social media, sir, in average siguro sir, magbigay na lang tayo ng estimate. Per week po, I'm just earning 1,500 per week with the food products na meron po ako, per week po iyon. Imagine niyo po sa isang buong buwan, nasa 6,000 lang po halos ang kinikita ko from my food products parang saying din ang pagod kasi the same ng ine-exert mon a pagod at effort, kakaunti ang customers at kakaunti ang sales na nagegenerate. Pero nung ako po ay gumamit ng social meida, naging x4 po. Naging x4 yung value from 6,000 naging 24,000 per month ang nagiging extra income ko po out of that product na dati naman ang liit ng income. Sa madaling sabi, napakalaki po... talagang legit na napakalaki because imagine po, from 6,000 per month ay naging 24,000 halos ang income per month ang nagiging income po natin out of that food product na minamarket po natin as of today. So, napakalaki po talaga, Sir!
F1222		
F1223		
F1224		
F1225		
F1226		
F1227		
F1228		
F1229		
F1230		
F1231		
F1232		
F1233		
F1234		
F1235		
F1236		
F1237		

Respondent 8 who is in a retail clothing business, explained that their previous 10% sales is now nine times more which is presently 90% because of the utilization of social media marketing particularly when they enter into live selling and Facebook posting.

Table 37 Respondent 8

H1569	Respondent 8	Sir, sobrang laki ng ano.. sobrang laki ng difference kasi for less than 1 year na through kumbaga... face to face selling, mga near places lang dito samin yung tintindahan naming, sobrang liit po ng market.. uhh... kumbaga yung sales naming sobrang limited lang parang dito lang kung may sampung customer dito sa area na 'to, ito lang. Pero nung time na ang-start po kami sa online, lumawak po kase ngayon may customer kami sa Visayas, meron na rin sa Mindanao kumbaga... dati, Baliuag lang or San Rafael. Yun lang po yung area na meron kaming kakilala or meron
H1570		
H1571		
H1572		
H1573		
H1574		
H1575		
H1575		

H1576 H1577 H1578 H1579 H1580 H1581 H1582 H1583 H1584 H1585 H1586 H1587	Respondent 8	kaming sinu-supply-an. Ngayon po, near provinces po like Tarlac, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, meron pa nga po sa Manila then sa Minadanao po and Visayas meron na rin po tayong sinu-supply-an na mga reseller don. Kumbaga po, yung difference sobrang laki po talaga. Kumbaga nga po, 10% po nung dating market ko, 90% po yung nadagdag... 9x po yung nangyare dun sa dati kong sales. Sobrang laki po ng online. Nung pinasok po naming yung pag-live at saka yung pag-ppost thru online.
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Respondent 4, who is in foods business also expressed, that when they started their Takoyakings business, they were not active on social media, and their sales was about 3,000-4,000 only in a day inclusive of labor expenses etc. According to Respondent 4, sales were a bit low but when they decided to use Facebook as their marketing platform, they received more orders and they established other franchise, that increased their sales.

Table 38 Respondent 4

D768 D769 D770 D771 D772 D773 D774	Respondent 4	From the start of Takoyakings, that time na di kami active sa social media, yung sales namin umaabot lang ng mga 3,000-4,000 a day so, andoon pa yung expenses namin sa tao etc., So, medyo mababa ang sales. So, nagdecide kami na gumamit na ng Facebook. Doon na kami nakatanggap ng iba't ibang orders. May mga nag-franchise na. Dahil sa social media, Malaki yung naging impact sa sales.
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➤ *Theme 3. Online Customers Behavior and Feedback*

The customer feedback and behavior are essential mediums for the delivery of customer appreciation and the sharing of positive and negative emotions which can have crucial implications on both business owners and customers.

Ordenes et al. (2014) presents a categorization of customer feedback and propose that customer feedback can be classified as 'explicit or implicit' depending on whether the customers consciously or unconsciously provide a third party with information about their experiences. However, social media use enables consumers to access sellers at their fingertips without leaving their homes, and marketers can receive real-time feedback that can tailor their marketing strategies or offer products and services that meet the consumers' needs (Singla & Durga, 2015).

This section of the research presents the considerable points on costumers' behavior and feedback based on lived experience of the respondents. It presents the perception of the respondents on dealing with real time customers behavior and feedback.

➤ *Subtheme 1: Positive Feedback and Comments*

The common appreciation among respondents is positive valence of a customer feedback for it is recognized as a form of customer engagement concerning quality goods and services, Respondent 9 who is in retail of clothing bsuiness, expressed her appreciation for receiving positive reviews. It encourages them to improve customers satisfaction. This should be done by continuously improving good customer relation and giving quality service.

Table 39 Respondent 9

I1824 I1825 I1826 I1827 I1828 I1829 I1830 I1831	Respondent 9	Ahh, yung sa mga positive naman naming, ofcourse, appreciate namin yung mga positive reviews... parang inaano na lang naming na... pag nag-uusap kami ng mga staff ko na, "How do we maintain that?" parang... how do we improve pa... kunyari, na-satisfy na sila, iisip kami ng way to satisfy them more or i-maintain namin yung ganong momentum na... hindi sila natatagalan sa order or yung na-ffriendly-han sila sa mga staff kaya sabi ko i-maintain lang yung ganon.
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Respondent 3, who is in retail of apparel business believed that good customer support depends on the products itself. This will be experienced through constant communication with the customers particularly the visibility of more positive reviews and feedbacks over social media

audience. Further, in the case of Respondent 3, who is in line with the retailing of clothes, the most FAQ or frequently asked question is about the sizes, as quoted "Hi, seller! What do you think is the size that I should get?". As sellers, sizes are recommended as what they see fit to the customer.

Table 40 Respondent 3

C559 C560 C561 C562 C563 C564 C565 C566 C567 C568	Respondent 3	I really believe na yung customer support really depends on the product itself kasi samen, super dali lang makipag-usap sa customer kase nakikita naman nila na madaming reviews, madaming feedbacks, so, ang most of the time na tanong lang nila is mostly sa size, like for example, “Hi, seller! What do you think is the size that I should get?” Parang we are just recommending them on what size. Normally, yun lang yung mga tanong, compare sa mga beauty siguro, uhh.. beauty industry, siguro yun yung mas mahirap na ano.. sa customer support. Pero, samen, di naman talaga siya mahirap.
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Product comments and reviews serve as main ingredients to have better and successful online business according to Respondent 6 who is in foods service business. He also added that this will be a positive reference to influence other consumers who also want to purchase the product as expressed in Line F1272 to F1274 . As cited by the Respondent 6; “ *Aba, masarap pala to. Nasarapan sila based sa comments, reviews and feedback kaya dapat mabili ko rin ito para matikman ko.*” It helps a lot and it’s a good thing for the business in Line F1277 to F1279.

According to Freeman et al. (2014), when consumers like, shares, and comments to a company social media page to receive timeline updates, any consumer engagement with company pages may appear in the news feed of another Facebook users. Thus, companies are able to effortlessly spread their marketing messages and brand images across multiple social networks (Griffiths & Casswell, 2010).

Table 41 Respondent 6

F1269 F1270 F1271 F1272 F1273 F1274 F1275 F1276 F1277 F1278 F1279	Respondent 6	Sir, ano po.. with regards to comments and reviews, isa rin yan sa masasabi ko na main ingredient kung bat nagiging successful ang mga online businesses because most of the time that is the reference... yan po ang reference ng mga new comers or mga new consumers na gusto mag-purchase ng product mo. They will think about what is the experience of the previous consumers na gumamit ng produkto na to bago ko bilhin ‘to. And, that will help them para magkaron sila ng idea na, “Aba, masarap pala to. Nasarapan sila based sa reviews and feedbacks kaya dapat mabili ko rin to para matikman ko.” Ayun, sir. Nakatulong po, malaking bagay po.
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Respondent 5 who is in retail apparel business emphasized that the satisfaction of customers is manifested through the positive reviews and feedbacks posted by consumers. It further helps the shops or business to reach additional customers.

Table 42 Respondent 5

E923 E924 E925 E926 E927 E928 E929 E930 E931	Respondent 5	Uhh... product brand and loyalty, yes. Kasi minsan, mostly our customers kapag na-service-an namin sila, kapag na-satisfied sila, nag-iiwan sila ng reviews and feedbacks. Syempre ang isang tao kasi na angtingin sa social media, even though sa mga online shopping, una mong tinitingnan bago ka bumili, reviews diba? So, pag maganda ang review ng company or ng shop na nakita mo, syempre tinutulungan niya na ma-convince ka na makabili or bumili ka sa shop na yon.
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➤ *Subtheme 2: Negative Feedback and Comments*

In Line I1838 to I1839, Respondent 9, who is in retail of clothing business received negative comment about the taste of coffee coming from one of their customers complaining about the bitter taste of their coffee, as the coffee did not meet the customer’s expectation. Respondent 9, further explained in Line I1840 to I1844, about their standard on what real coffee taste they have, and she added that they use original coffee bean for their coffee.

She also mentioned in Line I1845 to I1847, the common complaint of their customers is the deficiency of chairs inside the store, but they are really trying their best to accommodate those customers. They also encountered a complaint about crowd control, and they just give apology, in the form of discount and freebies.

Table 43 Respondent 9

I1834 I1835 I1836 I1837 I1838 I1839 I1840 I1841 I1842 I1843 I1844 I1845 I1846 I1847 I1848 I1849 I1850 I1851 I1852 I1853	Respondent 9	Marami. Depends on the situation kase uhm... dito kase sa Baliwag, what we offer is something new especially with the coffee, ang ano po naming sa coffee is medyo strong talaga. So, the market here yung want nila is on the sweeter side. So, usually nakukuha naming mga complains is, mapait yung coffee, hindi kalasa ng iba, yung preferred nilang café. So, we're trying to explain to them that this is our standard. Kaya po kami nagtayo ng café nag anito is to educate people din what real coffee is. So, parang if yung mga ganong complains po is ine-explain na lagn din po naming that we're using single origin beans kaya ganyan siya. Pero yung mga kunyari po, about sa service, sometimes it's really busy, tapos walang maupuan yung customers, so, we're trying our best para ma-accommodate sila lahat pero minsan po kasi, one time, nagkaron kaming complain regarding that na, we don't have crowd control. So, what we did is we said sorry, next time merong 20% off and sometimes din po pagka-medyo matagal yung service na nag-follow up sila, bibigyan po naming sila ng free cake para naman ma-feel better sila. Pero we apologize and we acknowledge naman po...
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Respondent 4, who is in foods service business also received negative feedback on the ingredients used in the products claiming that authentic ingredients (octopus) are lacking in the products. Late delivery is also another concern. As explained, they take time to explain to the customers the process of food preparation and proper queuing of orders.

Table 44 Respondent 4

D784 D785 D786 D787 D787A D787B D787C	Respondent 4	Pero syempre, meron ding mga feedback na bad, kagaya ng, wala daw octo sa loob, which is minsan hindi naming mapaniwalaan kasi nilalagay talaga namin bago yung butter niya. May iba ang strategy naman, sasabihin kulang sa mayo, kulang sa ganito also late daw yung delivery. And, ang cope up namin dyan is sinasabi namin may lineup tayo, maraming pending orders ganyan at freshly cooked po ang Takoyakings
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Comments cannot be avoided according to Respondent 7, who is in food service business. He cited that there are times they receive bulk orders especially during Christmas and New Year and late deliveries sometimes happen.

Respondent 7, who is in foods service business also explained that they do not have their own riders and they are just relying to third party. He also added and highlight the relevance of explaining the issue to the customers and that their complaints are attended to the best they can.

Table 45 Respondent 7

G1427 G1428 G1429 G1430 G1431 G1432 G1433 G1434	Respondent 7	Ohh yes. You can't avoid it. Everyday... hindi naman everyday, usually when there's time na it's Christmas and New Year, so you can't avoid it kase you'll have orders and sometimes you can't be able to get back to them on time or ma-late yung order nila dahil walang delivery. So, you just have to explain to them like, we don't have our own rider that we're just relying with a third party. You communicate to them that we tried our best to fulfill their orders.
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➤ *Subtheme 3: Downside of Online Selling*

Understanding social media customers is essential for a business company to find success for its current products as well as new product launches. Every consumer has a different thought process and attitude towards buying a

particular product online. According to Carrillat et al. (2014), in order to have such positive customer attitudes, hedonic aspects have to be carefully addressed in social media promotional activities to provide customer more intimate and pleasurable experiences.

The downside of Facebook use live selling is mainly on unclaimed and unpaid purchasers. This occurs when a claim of a customer of what is referred to as “mine” of the product did not complete the ordering or purchasing process of paying for the product. There are also those who use dummy accounts or “trolls” who do not follow through or respond to the seller after claim if the product has been made.

Also, Respondent 2, who is in retail of nature seeds business, Line B259 to B262 implies the blocking of customers so as not to disrupt them with their business page and at the same time they can no longer view and see their Facebook page.

Table 46 Respondent 2

B235 B236 B237 B238 B239 B240 B241 B242	Respondent 2	Example po niyan sir, halimbawa po, mag-live kayo, hindi po natin maiiwasan na may mag-mamine tapos hindi naman po nila kukunin. Mayroon din pong nag-troll gamit yung dummy accounts nila. Pero since po, nagbebenta ka nga po, syempre itatabi niyo po ‘yun bale ibigay niyo po sakanila since sila ‘yung unang nag-mine. Ang ano lang po n’on is pag minessage niyo na sila, hindi na sila nagreply or bino-block ka na po nila.
B257 B258	Researcher	Ahh, ma’am pwede ko bang malaman kung ano ang ibig sabihin ng auto-ban?
B259 B260 B261 B262	Respondent 2	Ahh, agad-agad po naming silang bino-block sa page para hindi na po sila makapang-abala at the same time hindi na po nila ma-view yung aming page kasi po mali na po yung ginawa nila eh hassle na po pag umulit pa sila sa amin.

The use of Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunity and Threats (SWOT) Analysis has been emphasized by Respondent 9. It is done to search for unpredictable market behavior. Addressing those unpredictable behavior is what respondent 9 would like to realize. To help the interest of the customers and to sustain the relevance of the product, it is important to continuously improve and innovate their products.

Respondent 9 also mentioned that the threat includes the establishment of other coffee shops with the same concept in the same areas. However, she believes that this threat could be best addressed by being true to their customers and by continuously providing high quality service.

Table 47 Respondent 9

I1857 I1858 I1859 I1860 I1861 I1862 I1863 I1864 I1865 I1866 I1867 I1868	Respondent 9	<i>Yes po. Actually, meron pa kong ginawa yung mga SWOT Analysis. Nag-research kami about unpredictable market behavior. Naisip na rin po naming ‘yun. How do we address those unpredictable behavior? Kasi baka mamaya, nagsawa na yung mga tao so, we have to innovate products, we have to offer them something new every season. Tapos pag sa mga threats naman regarding sa, maraming magtatayo ng café na similar to ours, ang ano naman po naming is as long as we are true to our customers, yung kung ano talaga yung mission and vision naming na i-provide talaga sa kanila yung high quality ng food and service, I don’t think na oit’s gonna be a problem po.</i>
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The problem experienced by the Respondent 8 arises from the customer’s demand for product replacement. He explained that if the customer’s problem remain unattended there is a tendency for customers to find another supplier. It is very important to address customers’ concerns especially product damages.

Table 48 Respondent 8

H1637 H1638 H1639 H1640 H1641 H1642 H1643 H1644 H1645	Respondent 8	Kasi, once po kasi na hindi natin binigyan ng actions yung ganon na problem, magiging cause pa po yun na hindi na sa atin kumuha ulit or humanap ng ibang supplier. Kaya lahat po ng customer’s concern nag anon, sinasabi na naming na... “Ma’am/Sir, if ever po na may damage yung item naming, ibabalik po naming sayo.” Pangkaraniwan po kasing problem yung may maliit nab utas kasi di na po naming ma-check lahat kasi umaabot po ng 5,000-10,000 stocks kaya di na po maisaisa. Ang gingagawa din po naming don, ni-rerefund din po naming sa supplier.
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H1646		
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In the online store industry, it is inevitable not to encounter bogus buyer. Respondent 6 who is in foods service business, has his own system of verifying orders to avoid having customers who do not pay for the orders made. It stresses out that if somebody is ordering food online, as an online store owner he makes sure that it is in a cash on delivery basis and at the same time ensures the identity or proof of customers address and prevent scam scenario with regards to product payment. Cash on delivery is the safest way in online platform specifically for small businesses because compared to Shopee and Lazada shops who offers different payment methods can still recover if they encounter what they called “bogus buyer”.

Table 49 Respondent 6

F1283	Respondent 6	Sir, in the online store industry, it is inevitable po para sa atin na hindi tayo maka-encounter ng isang bogus buyer. So, for me, I changed the system that I have because I already experienced that particular scenario wherein someone ordered a lot of my food products and they don't even pay for it kasi daw po ibang account daw po yung gumamit. Kumbaga, they are misleading us para doon sa totoong consumer na bumili talaga. Ibig sabihin po, wala talagang consumer na mag-coconsume ng produktong ginawa ko. So, what will be the action of me, bilang isang store owner sa online na gumagamit ng social media platform? You need to have a verification process, hindi pwede nap ag umorder sayo ay... lalo't hindi mo kakilala ay i-accept mo agad. You need to provide atleast... lalo na kung ang order system mo is cash on delivery na upon delivery saka lang siya babayaran syempre dapat may identification man lang yung pag-dedeli-ver-an mo para proof na siya talaga ay residente ng lugar nap ag-dedeli-ver-an mo. On the other hand po, pwede na rin nating ma-prevent yung ganong mga scenario na na-scam tayo thru payment, gawin natin why not cash first, before we deliver the food. That is the safest way po in online platform lalo na po sa mga small businesses kasi hindi naman tayo katulad ng mga Shopee or Lazada na amy malaking pera para magpaluwal dun sa mga payment na binibigay ng mga online customers. We're just a small business and I think the most possible way to control those scams is to be preventive. Cash first basis po yung gawin natin.
F1284		
F1285		
F1286		
F1287		
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Based on the shared experience of the respondent, from time to time they are searching their own product on Shopee and Lazada and they found out that some sellers are using their own product, own title and product description. They directly send message to them to delete it. Respondent 3 who is in retail of apparel business, Line C575 to C579.

Chinese people are most of the time the one who copied and imitated their product description in a form of product hunting particularly if they see and observe that business is profitable by generating more sales online, respondent also added that nowadays, consumers are so wise with regards to product purchase because of relying to customers feedback, comment and reviews. Line C581 to C585.

Table 50 Respondent 3

C575	Respondent 3	Uhh.. we experienced that. Kasi minsan, from time to time, we are searching our own product on Shopee and Lazada and we found out that some sellers are using our own product, they're using our own title and description and yeah, we are just messaging them to delete it. Most of the time, they are Chinese people, like they are product hunting on the platform so, they're doing that, maybe they think it's profitable dahil nakikita nil ana amdaming sales. Akala nil ana mabibilhan din sila ganon, pero yeah, ngayon naman pwede mo naman sila i-message and I think, buyer is also wise na pag wala naman sila nakitang review, hindi naman nila bibilhan.
C576		
C577		
C578		
C579		
C580		
C581		
C582		
C583		
C584		
C585		

V. CONCLUSIONS

➤ *Theme 1: Strong Business and Marketing Viability*

In the first theme, participants described their strong business marketing viability in varied ways. Several subthemes emerged relating to emerging customer interpenetration, top social media marketing platform and influence of liking, sharing and commenting.

- *Subtheme A: Emerging Customer Interpenetration.*

The experience with regards to emerging customer penetration is highlighted by micro business entities respondents as they share their phenomenological responses about the rising number of their online customers with the utilization of social media as marketing channel.

- *Subtheme B: Top Social Media Marketing Platform.*

Another subtheme which emerged from the interviews was the top social media marketing platform. They utilized Facebook as their FB business page, FB ads, and live selling as realizable medium for product advertising, promotion and selling, they also maximize the use of Facebook platform to link their products to Shopee and Lazada. Furthermore, a partial number of respondents detail the use of another social platform like Instagram, YouTube, Google and the likes.

- *Subtheme C: Influence of Liking, Sharing and Tagging.*

The last subtheme under strong marketing viability relates to the influence of customer likes, shares and tags. Respondents discussed the robust effect of those reactions to their online business which can simply reach out a surprising number of target customers primarily.

➤ *Theme 2: Interactive and Promising Platform Channel*

The second theme which emerged in the interviews is the interactive and promising platform channel. All participants cited some promising benefits about the application of social media marketing. Most of the respondents stated their experience about the promising used of Facebook Page, Facebook Ads, Online Market place, Facebook live selling, Instagram and YouTube as their sales and marketing platform.

- *Subtheme A: Traditional and Unconventional Marketing Comparability.*

The use of two marketing method demonstrates the dissimilar effects to sales and marketing among SMEs respondents. However, micro business entities lived experience showed a very prominent comparison between the use of traditional and unconventional marketing approach, where most of the respondents figure out the average increase of sales and marketing using modern marketing compared to the traditional method.

- *Subtheme B: Leverage Digital Marketing Stratagems.*

Most business publicity using the social media marketing appeals to influence the way how business consumers view themselves and how buying a certain product can prove to be beneficial and effective. Respondents described the use of different digital marketing

platforms to leverage consumer numbers that is seems to be an unheralded strategy for them to be more attractive to the customers and develop a product-centric groups in such a way that ties the sellers and customers engagement.

- *Subtheme C: Realizable Customer Reach.*

The potential number of customers coverage was discussed by the micro business entities owners that can massively broaden and reach through social media marketing channel like Facebook page, Facebook live selling, Facebook ads, Facebook market place, Instagram, YouTube and the like. Most of the respondents stated that they are being visible regions in Luzon, Visayas and Mindanao.

- *Subtheme D: Insistent Sales and Marketing Appreciation.*

As mentioned by the respondents, relative to their sales and marketing scheme, the extensive escalation via Facebook medium contributed to the vertical appreciation of their online sales and marketing tactic respectively.

➤ *Theme 3: Online Customers Behavior and Feedback*

The last theme which emerged in the interviews is the different online comments, feedback and consumer behavior from the online customers. These are categorized as positive comments and feedback; the negative comments and feedback and the behavior of social media customers as encountered by the respondents.

- *Subtheme A: Positive Feedback and Comments.*

Having good positive comments and feedback is considered as one of the core ingredients for business success according to (Respondent 6; While Respondent 9 realize the dynamic importance of positive comments for business sustainability.

- *Subtheme B: Negative Feedback and Comment.*

Negative feedback and comments cannot be avoided as stated by Respondent 7. While, Respondent 4 explains that accepting negative comments and feedback is a source for product improvement. However, Respondent 9 offers apology and explanation to customers who throw negative comments but most of the time they do offer freebies and give aways for such customers.

- *Subtheme C: Downside of Online Selling.*

Understanding the different attitudes of social media customers is really vital to cope up to the emergent number of reliable and trust worthy consumers. As such, micro business entity owners critically show their tolerance and broadmindedness to those possible customers, need-based shoppers, bogus miner, troll customers, imitator and those customers having fake and dummy account.

➤ *Based on the Finding of this Study, the following were Concluded:*

Social media marketing plays a crucial role in the business of micro business entity owners. Social media enables communication not only one's personal life but also for business life of micro business entities. However, the use

of social media as sales and marketing platforms gained a lot of confidence in the life of micro business entity business owners.

The strong business and marketing viability through the use of social media marketing can be clearly and perceptibly observed in a more divergent platform channel wherein business persons reach out a greater number of people as well as the mass number of social media users. Moreover, the top most digital channel for sales and marketing has been realized, particularly the use of Facebook page, Facebook ads, Facebook market place, Facebook live selling, YouTube, Instagram and Google as quantified by the micro business entity owners and managers.

Micro business entity owners and managers correspondingly described the social media as an interactive and promising platform channel, this can evidently be identified through their experience with regards to the comparative analysis of practicing traditional to modern method of marketing which constitute as the most prevalent factors that justified the quantifiable increase of micro business entity product sales and marketing. On the other hand, the influence of social media marketing strategies made by micro business entities is a big factor for generating a massive number of customers. Likewise, customers reach through social media marketing encompasses a wide range of strategies and yields a domino effect in terms of sales and revenue as perceived by the micro business entities respondents.

Online customers feedback and comments, whether positive or negative, serve as fundamental components for business success and it is very evident that creating customer and retaining them is very important. This can be done only by understanding and paying attention towards the different consumer's online buying behavior. Downside of online selling as experienced by the owners and managers is indeed a great challenge to micro business entities predominantly those troll customers having fake and dummy account, bogus miner and imitator.

RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *From the findings and Conclusion of the Study, the following Recommendations are Provided.*

- The micro business entity owners are advised to track other medium of social media marketing channel aside from Facebook, YouTube, Instagram and Google. The use of other versatile platform like Twitter and Tiktok is highly recommended for it can deliver higher returns of sales leading to an exponential growth and sustainable customer also.
- Most micro business entity managers and employees are painfully familiar with those negative feedback and product reviews. It is recommended that each review and feedback has to be addressed always by checking the situation that needs to be attended as soon as possible. On this matter, such negative reviews may

turn into positive that will soon lead the micro business to gain online reputation by taking over the responsibility for the online customers.

- It is also imperative for future micro business entities to have a definite and written online marketing plan that outlines their marketing goals aside from sales and marketing, wherein the strategies, timelines, other marketing channels, customer records and budget are properly incorporated.
- It is recommended for micro business entities to embrace development in technology by testing and adapting the new advancement for their business particularly the social media marketing transformation by exploring social media marketing opportunities; and formulating a dynamic social media strategy that can expansively reach not only the online "Local Customers" but also those probable customers in other country.
- It is also recommended to micro business entity owners, managers and employees to maximize the use of other online shopping platform in the Philippines aside from Facebook and Instagram associated to Shopee and Lazada. For a more winning selling strategy, it is recommended to utilize other platform shopping networks linkages like OLX, Zalora, Metro Deal, Galleon, E-bay Philippines and the likes.
- The best protection a consumer has is to be well informed about his rights and responsibilities as detailed in Consumer act RA 7394. Consumers should be ready to secure, protect, and assert their rights in the online marketplace while trading and transacting business to obtain fair value at all times. It is recommended to heighten consumer vigilance for quality and safe products and services by utilizing available information on products and services that will help them to make wise buying decision.
- To ensure security of transactions and personal information using social media marketing channels. Micro business entity consumers should be well aware of their roles and responsibilities which, at a minimum, include the following; check for the right and secure SME's business website before doing any online business transactions or sending personal information. Customers should make sure that correct business website has been accessed and check if the website is "secured" by checking the Universal Resource Locators (URLs) which should begin with "https" and a closed padlock icon on the status bar in the browser displayed, to confirm the authenticity of the site by displaying a security certificate information of the business site.
- It is vital to be aware of social media usage for it is considered as a living resume that showcases the character, therefore, the academic community should always be educated and mindful by sensibly exercising the proper use of social media marketing proactively.
- Maintaining a good Facebook media page requires more than pushing out a business message. It is recommended to engage with the customers with detailed online business content and information that would be of great interest to cultivate pleasant business conversation between customers and online sellers.

- Future studies can explore the effects of using multi-channel and omni channel marketing to examine and recognize the seamless experience of online customers.

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